

Scalar Field of Measurability Applied to 3D Systems - Central $\frac{K}{r}$ Potential

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Introduction

This paper builds on the concepts introduced and the methods developed in the paper titled **“Special Relativity’s Light-Signal Mediated Definition of Synchronism is Without Contradictions Only in Phase Space When Considering the Quantum Behavior of Light”** [1], applying them generally to 3D (configuration space) systems, and specifically to the central potential $\frac{K}{r}$ (e.g., hydrogenic atom) system. Results include the characteristic discrete spectra for radial and angular motion exhibited by the canonical model, as well as spatial probability density distributions matching the orbital geometry – including nuanced features – of the canonical model.

5.3 Application to Systems in 3 Dimensions

We assume that the concept of probability density of measurable presence described above applies generally to any dimension of any coordinate system (e.g., spherical, cylindrical, etc.), and not just to a single axis in a Cartesian coordinate system.

We make the additional assumption that the probability density of measurable presence of a particle in 3 dimensions can be obtained by combining the probability density of measurable presence for that particle in each dimension, with the probability density of measurable presence at a location in 3-space being the algebraic product of the probability density of measurable presence of that particle in each dimension. For example, in spherical coordinates, the probability density of measurable presence at location (r, θ, ϕ) is:

$$P_{mp}(r, \theta, \phi) = P_{mp}(r) \cdot P_{mp}(\theta) \cdot P_{mp}(\phi)$$

These two assumptions will be employed in our description of the Central-Potential system using spherical coordinates.

6.4 Central-Potential: $V(r) = \frac{K_{radial}}{r} + \frac{K_{angular}}{r^2}$

We will now apply the model to the description of the motion of a particle moving in 3 dimensions, subject to a central $\frac{K}{r}$ potential, bound in a planar elliptical orbit characterized in the usual way by the major and minor axes of the ellipse, based on the constants of motion — the energy E and the magnitude and orientation (e.g., w.r.t. the polar axis) of the orbital angular momentum L — with the source of the central potential at one focus of the elliptical orbit. We employ the spherical coordinate system to describe the probability density of measurable presence in 3 dimensions and to determine the spectral indices of the constants of motion. Noting that the orbital plane is orthogonal to the angular momentum vector, we choose the corresponding fixed orientation of the plane of the elliptical orbit also to be relative to the polar axis, with the major axis at some angle of declination $0 \leq \tau \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$ (“ τ ” for “tilt”) from the polar axis z (doubly degenerate w.r.t. polar orientation) and with the minor axis parallel to the plane $z = 0$. This representation is illustrated in the following plots:

As we see in analysis of the angular probability of measurability, the azimuthal (ϕ) orientation of the major axis of the elliptical orbit corresponding to a given set of angular momentum spectral indices is indeterminate (a correlate of any azimuthal orientation yielding the same angular momentum magnitude and polar orientation). That is, the orbital ellipse major axis azimuthal orientation is infinitely degenerate. This can be visualized as a revolution of the ellipse(s) and major axes around the polar axis in the following plots showing the conical surface of revolution of the ellipse major axis and the curved surface of revolution of the declined ellipse itself:

Orbital Ellipse Declined from Polar (z) Axis (n=7, l=5)
 Periapsis=(0, 0, ±14.7071), Apoapsis=(0, 0, ±83.2929, ->Z=69.6878, ->XY=45.6214)
 a=49.0, b=35.0, e=0.699854, ppu(n=7,l=5,m=-3), phs=0, Vpt=, ViewPoint->[1.3,-2.4,2]
 Lvec=ArcCos[Abs[MM]/Sqrt[LL*(LL + 1)]]
 Apex Angles: Lvec(θ=0.315495*Pi), OrbitalPlaneDeclination(θ=-0.184505*Pi)

Orbital Ellipse Declined from Polar (z) Axis (n=7, l=5)
 Periapsis=(0, 0, ±14.7071), Apoapsis=(0, 0, ±83.2929, ->Z=69.6878, ->XY=45.6214)
 a=49.0, b=35.0, e=0.699854, ppu(n=7,l=5,m=-3), phs=0, Vpt=, ViewPoint->[Infinity,0,0]
 Lvec=ArcCos[Abs[MM]/Sqrt[LL*(LL + 1)]]
 Apex Angles: Lvec(θ=0.315495*Pi), OrbitalPlaneDeclination(θ=-0.184505*Pi)

The geometry of these elliptical orbit orientations will be important in describing the angular probabilities of measurability and presence in later sections.

6.4.1 Composed Description

Description of the central potential system is formulated in terms of radial motion, and polar and azimuthal angular motion.

We now compose a description of this 3D system from a combination of three 1-dimensional descriptions in the spherical coordinate system (ρ, θ, ϕ) , where θ represents polar angular measure and ϕ represents azimuthal angular measure. The 3-dimensional description consists of a 3-dimensional probability density distribution of measurable presence and the spectral indices of the constants of motion (energy and angular momentum magnitude and polar orientation) satisfying constraints imposed by physical properties of the system. The 3-dimensional probability density distribution of measurable presence is the algebraic product of the values of P_{mp} for each coordinate:

$$P_{mp}(r, \theta, \phi) = P_{mp}(r) \cdot P_{mp}(\theta) \cdot P_{mp}(\phi)$$

This product of probability densities describes the probability density of measurable presence at any point in 3-dimensional configuration space as a function of the total energy E , angular momentum magnitude l , and polar orientation of the orbital angular momentum vector (corresponding to an orbital-ellipse declined at an angle τ from the polar axis). *We will see that this approach yields a 3-dimensional probability density distribution that is similar to that which results from solutions of the Schrodinger equation for the hydrogenic atom in canonical quantum mechanics.*

Starting with the Hamiltonian for the central-potential system, using the reduced mass μ for the system having the potential $V(r) = \frac{K}{r}$ (with $K = -Ze^2$, $K = -Gm_1 \cdot m_2$, etc.):

$$H = \frac{p_r^2}{2\mu} + \frac{L^2}{2\mu r^2} + \frac{K}{r}$$

With total energy E and total angular momentum L being constants of the motion, we have:

$$E = \frac{1}{2\mu} \left(p_r^2 + \frac{L^2}{r^2} \right) + \frac{K}{r}$$

Solving this equation for p_r (which we will later use to derive $P_m(r)$), we obtain:

$$p_r = \pm \sqrt{2\mu \left(E - \frac{K}{r} \right) - \frac{L^2}{r^2}}$$

6.4.2 Radial Probability Density Distribution $P_{mp}(r)$

We first apply the method developed above for deriving P_m to the radial dimension in spherical coordinates to obtain $P_m(r)$. We start by obtaining the expression for $P_m(r)$ in both phase and configuration space, and subsequently obtain the expression for $P_p(r)$ in configuration space to finally obtain an expression for $P_{mp}(r)$ in configuration space.

6.4.2.1 In Phase Space

We first derive the expression for $P_m(\alpha)$ in phase space. This result, along with spectral indices for the constants of motion derived from imposing boundary conditions, will subsequently be used to derive $P_m(r)$ in configuration space.

6.4.2.1.1 Form of $P_m(\alpha)$ in Phase Space

Following the method applied to polynomial potentials, we define non-dimensional radial position and radial momentum variables in phase space.

In parametric form, for phase space, with central angle α , we define:

$$\mathbf{r} \equiv \frac{E}{K} r$$

$$\mathbf{p}_r \equiv \frac{p_r}{\sqrt{2\mu E}}$$

This allows us to write the Hamiltonian as:

$$1 = \mathbf{p}_r^2 + \frac{EL^2}{2\mu K^2} \cdot \frac{1}{\mathbf{r}^2} + \frac{1}{\mathbf{r}}$$

giving for \mathbf{p}_r :

$$p_r = \pm \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{r}\right) - \frac{EL^2}{2\mu K^2} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2}}$$

In phase space, we define r as:

$$r = \cos(\alpha)$$

with which we can obtain a parametric expression for p_r in terms of α

$$p_r = \pm \sqrt{\left(1 - \sec(\alpha)\right) - \frac{EL^2}{2\mu K^2} \sec^2(\alpha)}$$

Equating expressions for p_r and for r , we obtain parametric expressions, in terms of α , for r :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{E}{K} r &= \cos(\alpha) \\ r(\alpha) &= \frac{K}{E} \cos(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

and for p_r :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{p_r(\alpha)}{\sqrt{2\mu E}} &= \pm \sqrt{\left(1 - \sec(\alpha)\right) - \frac{EL^2}{2\mu K^2} \sec^2(\alpha)} \\ p_r(\alpha) &= \pm \sqrt{2\mu E} \sqrt{\left(1 - \sec(\alpha)\right) - \frac{EL^2}{2\mu K^2} \sec^2(\alpha)} \end{aligned}$$

Next, we obtain the expression for $\frac{r p_r}{h}$ in phase space:

$$\frac{r(\alpha) p_r(\alpha)}{h} = \left(\frac{1}{h}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{K}{E} \cos(\alpha)\right)_r \cdot \left(\sqrt{2\mu E} \sqrt{\left(1 - \sec(\alpha)\right) - \frac{EL^2}{2\mu K^2} \sec^2(\alpha)}\right)_{p_r}$$

Multiplying the last term under the radical by $\frac{h^2}{h^2}$ and regrouping some factors, we obtain:

$$\frac{r(\alpha) p_r(\alpha)}{h} = \sqrt{\frac{2\mu K^2}{h^2 E}} \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{\left(1 - \sec(\alpha)\right) - \frac{E h^2}{2\mu K^2} \cdot \frac{L^2}{h^2} \cdot \sec^2(\alpha)}$$

Next, by distributing $\cos(\alpha)$ within the radical, we finally obtain:

$$\frac{r(\alpha) p_r(\alpha)}{h} = \sqrt{\frac{2\mu K^2}{h^2 E}} \sqrt{\cos(\alpha) [\cos(\alpha) - 1] - \frac{E h^2}{2\mu K^2} \frac{L^2}{h^2}}$$

which we use in the expression for $P_m(\alpha)$ in phase space:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 \left[\pi \sqrt{\frac{2\mu K^2}{h^2 E}} \sqrt{\cos(\alpha) [\cos(\alpha) - 1] - \frac{E h^2}{2\mu K^2} \frac{L^2}{h^2}} \right]$$

6.4.2.1.2 Applying Boundary Conditions

For the radial probability density distribution in the elliptical orbit of a central-potential system, we expect the probability of measurability to vanish at (or near) the apoapsis and periapsis of the elliptical orbit, as these are the turning points of radial motion. This condition is met by requiring that $P_m = 0$ at the angles α_e in phase space:

$$P_m(\alpha_e) = \cos^2 \left[\pi \frac{r(\alpha_e) p_r(\alpha_e)}{\hbar} - \Phi \right] = 0$$

This condition can be expressed by a phase angle $\Phi = \frac{\pi}{2}$ and the relation:

$$\pi \frac{r(\alpha_e) p_r(\alpha_e)}{\hbar} = q\pi, \quad (q \in \mathbb{Z})$$

From our results for polynomial potentials in the preceding section, we now proceed to impose separate boundary conditions for the $\frac{1}{r^2}$ and $\frac{1}{r}$ terms of the potential. As the value of L is independent of E , the order in which we impose boundary conditions is inconsequential.

6.4.2.1.2.1 For Potential Term r^{-2} :

Using the value $\alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{2}$ for the $\frac{1}{r^2}$ term in this potential, the boundary condition amounts to (using l for q):

$$\pi \sqrt{\frac{2\mu K^2}{\hbar^2 E}} \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \left[\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{E\hbar^2}{2\mu K^2} \frac{L^2}{\hbar^2}} = l\pi$$

From which, we obtain the result:

$$\sqrt{\frac{2\mu K^2}{\hbar^2 E}} \cdot \left(-\frac{E\hbar^2}{2\mu K^2} \frac{L^2}{\hbar^2} \right) = l$$

$$L^2 = -\hbar^2 l^2$$

6.4.2.1.2.2 For Potential Term r^{-1} :

Using the value $\alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{3}$ for the $\frac{1}{r}$ term in this potential, the boundary condition amounts to (using n for q):

$$\pi \sqrt{\frac{2\mu K^2}{\hbar^2 E}} \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) \left[\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{E\hbar^2}{2\mu K^2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\hbar^2} \cdot (-\hbar^2 l^2) \right)} = n\pi$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{2\mu K^2}{\hbar^2 E}} \sqrt{\frac{E\hbar^2}{2\mu K^2} \cdot l^2 - \frac{1}{4}} = n$$

$$\sqrt{l^2 - \frac{\mu K^2}{2\hbar^2 E}} = n$$

From which we obtain:

$$l^2 - \frac{\mu K^2}{2\hbar^2 E_{nl}} = n^2$$

6.4.2.1.3 Expression for Radial Energy

Solving the above equation for the energy, we obtain:

$$E_{nl} = - \frac{\mu K^2}{2\hbar^2 (n^2 - l^2)}$$

Two restrictions on the spectral indices n and l are immediately evident:

1. The value of l must be less than the value of n ; otherwise, the energy is infinite in the case $l = n$ or positive in the case $l > n$ (which is inconsistent with being a bound system).
2. The value of n cannot be zero; otherwise, the energy is positive (given the above constraints on l).

It is also noteworthy that this energy varies with the angular momentum of the system, whereas the total energy of the system is a constant, regardless of how that energy is distributed among radial potential, radial kinetic and angular kinetic (there being no angular potential in a central-potential system). Evidently, this energy is only the radial portion of the total system energy. We can find the total system energy by considering this expression when the system has no angular momentum (i.e., $l = 0$). In this case, all the energy of the system must be due only to radial displacement and motion (i.e., the sum of radial-potential and radial-kinetic energy):

$$E_n = - \frac{\mu K^2}{2\hbar^2 n^2}$$

This energy is recognized as the energy of the hydrogenic atom in the canonical model, with $K = Ze^2$:

$$E_n = - \frac{\mu (Ze^2)^2}{2\hbar^2 n^2}$$

6.4.2.1.4 Expression for $P_m(\alpha)$ in Phase Space

Following the method we applied to simple polynomial potentials, we substitute the values obtained for the constants of the motion (E and L) into the central-potential specific form for $P_m(\alpha)$ obtained above, and with the definition:

$$N \equiv \sqrt{4(n^2 - l^2)}$$

we obtain the expression for $P_m(\alpha)$ in phase space (recognizing the identity

$$\cos\left(\alpha - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \sin(\alpha):$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P_m(\alpha) &= \sin^2 \left[\pi \sqrt{\frac{2\mu K^2}{\hbar^2} \cdot \left(-\frac{2\hbar^2(n^2-l^2)}{\mu K^2}\right)} \sqrt{\cos(\alpha)[\cos(\alpha) - 1] - \left(-\frac{\mu K^2}{2\hbar^2(n^2-l^2)}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu K^2}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{-\hbar^2 l^2}{\hbar^2}\right)} \right] \\
&= \sin^2 \left[\pi \sqrt{4(n^2 - l^2)} \sqrt{\cos(\alpha)[\cos(\alpha) - 1] - \frac{l^2}{4(n^2-l^2)}} \right] \\
&= \sin^2 \left[\pi N \sqrt{\cos(\alpha)[\cos(\alpha) - 1] - \frac{l^2}{N^2}} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Recalling that in an earlier step of the analysis we distributed $\cos(\alpha)$ within the radical expression for $p_r(\alpha)$, we now factor $\cos(\alpha)$ back out of the radical to obtain an expression for

$P_m(\alpha)$ strictly in terms of $\frac{r(\alpha) \cdot p_r(\alpha)}{\hbar}$:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \sin^2 \left[\pi \cdot N \cos(\alpha) \cdot \sqrt{[1 - \sec(\alpha)] - \frac{l^2}{N^2} \sec^2(\alpha)} \right]$$

where we have:

$$r(\alpha) = N \cos(\alpha)$$

$$p_r(\alpha) = \sqrt{[1 - \sec(\alpha)] - \frac{l^2}{N^2} \sec^2(\alpha)}$$

As the expression under the radical is proportional to the square of the momentum, we use its absolute value to obtain a real value for the momentum, giving the final expression for $P_m(\alpha)$:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \sin^2 \left[\pi \cdot N \cos(\alpha) \cdot \sqrt{\left| [1 - \sec(\alpha)] - \frac{l^2}{N^2} \sec^2(\alpha) \right|} \right]$$

6.4.2.1.5 Graphical Depiction in Phase Space

The following plots (for this illustration, $n = 5$, $l = 2$) parallel those already shown for the polynomial potentials in phase space earlier.

For the following plots:

1. Plot **(a)** depicts the phase space trajectory.
2. Plot **(b)**: depicts the phase space trajectory through the scalar field, illustrating why the value of P_m varies as it does along that trajectory shown in plot **(c)**. For each plot, the

scalar field is expressed in terms of the spectral index $N \equiv \sqrt{4(n^2 - l^2)}$ of this system:

$$P_m = \cos^2 \left[\left(\pi \cdot N \cdot r \cdot p_r \right) - \frac{\pi}{2} \right]$$

3. Plot **(c)** depicts P_m along the phase space trajectory.

4. Plot **(d)** depicts the parallel projection of **(c)** onto the $r - P_m(r)$ plane in configuration space.
5. Plot **(e)** depicts the space-like segment of P_m along the phase space trajectory.
6. Plot **(f)** depicts the parallel projection of **(e)** onto the $r - P_m(r)$ plane in configuration space.

6.4.2.2 In Configuration Space

We will next follow the process established above for deriving $P_m(x)$ in configuration space for a polynomial potential to derive $P_m(r)$ in configuration space.

6.4.2.2.1 Form of $P_m(r)$

In order to derive the parallel projection of $P_m(\alpha)$ onto configuration space, we use the method employed for the polynomial potentials earlier, as we substitute $\frac{E}{K}r$ for $\cos(\alpha)$ into the form of the equation for $P_m(\alpha)$ above. First, obtaining the expression for $\frac{E}{K}$ for this system (with $\Xi = \frac{\sqrt{2\mu|K|}}{\hbar}$, where the units of Ξ are $[\Xi] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{[\text{length}]}}$) by using the expression for E_N obtained by imposing the boundary conditions above, we obtain (recognizing that for this system, K is an algebraically negative value):

$$\frac{E_N}{K} = -\frac{2\mu K^2}{\hbar^2 N^2} \cdot \frac{1}{K} = \frac{2\mu|K|}{\hbar^2 N^2} = \frac{\Xi^2}{N^2}$$

This gives us for $\cos(\alpha)$:

$$\cos(\alpha) = \frac{\Xi^2}{N^2} \cdot r$$

The expression for the radial probability density distribution in configuration space is then:

$$\begin{aligned} P_m(r) &= \sin^2 \left[\pi \cdot N \cdot \left(\frac{\Xi^2}{N^2} \cdot r \right) \cdot \sqrt{\left[1 - \left(\frac{N^2}{\Xi^2} \cdot \frac{1}{r} \right) \right] - \frac{l^2}{N^2} \left(\frac{N^2}{\Xi^2} \cdot \frac{1}{r} \right)^2} \right] \\ &= \sin^2 \left[\pi \cdot \frac{\Xi^2}{N} \cdot r \cdot \sqrt{\left| 1 - \left(\frac{N^2}{\Xi^2} \cdot \frac{1}{r} \right) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{l^2}{\Xi^2} \cdot \frac{1}{r} \right) \right|} \right] \\ &= \sin^2 \left[\pi \cdot \frac{\Xi^2}{N} \cdot r \cdot \sqrt{\frac{N^2}{\Xi^2} \cdot \left| \frac{\Xi^2}{N^2} - \frac{1}{r} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{l^2}{\Xi^2} \cdot \frac{1}{r} \right) \right|} \right] \\ &= \sin^2 \left[\pi \Xi r \sqrt{\left| \left[\frac{\Xi}{N} \right]^2 - \frac{1}{r} \left(1 + \left[\frac{l}{\Xi} \right]^2 \frac{1}{r} \right) \right|} \right] \end{aligned}$$

6.4.2.2.1.1 Orbital Ellipse Properties in Terms of Spectral Indices

We next examine the properties of an elliptical orbit resulting from the $\frac{1}{r}$ central potential, including the semi-major (a) and semi-minor (b) axes, and the resulting orbital ellipse eccentricity (ϵ).

Recalling from Newtonian mechanics the properties of a central-potential elliptical orbit in terms of constants of the motion:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \left| \frac{K}{2E} \right| \\ \epsilon &= \sqrt{1 + \frac{2EL^2}{\mu K^2}} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{b^2}{a^2}} \end{aligned}$$

we determine the following (from the definition of ϵ in terms of a and b):

$$+ \frac{2EL^2}{\mu K^2} = - \frac{b^2}{a^2}$$

from which we obtain:

$$b^2 = - \frac{L^2}{2\mu|E|}$$

Keeping in mind that the energy E in these expressions for orbital ellipse properties is the total energy of the system (radial potential + radial kinetic + angular kinetic), we use the spectral index form of E , which represents the total system energy (E_n), rather than the form that represents radial-only energy (E_N), along with the angular momentum spectral index (l), to derive the expressions of elliptical orbit properties in terms of spectral indices:

$$a = \left| \frac{K}{2E} \right| = \left| \frac{K}{2} \cdot \left(-\frac{2\hbar^2 n^2}{\mu K^2} \right) \right| = \frac{\hbar^2 n^2}{\mu |K|}$$

$$b = \sqrt{-\frac{(-\hbar^2 l^2)}{2\mu} \cdot \left| -\frac{2\hbar^2 n^2}{\mu K^2} \right|} = \frac{\hbar^2 n l}{\mu |K|}$$

From this, we derive an expression for the eccentricity of the orbital ellipse in terms of the energy and angular momentum spectral indices. Given that:

$$\frac{b}{a} = \frac{\hbar^2 n l}{\mu |K|} \cdot \frac{\mu |K|}{\hbar^2 n^2} = \frac{l}{n}$$

we obtain:

$$\epsilon = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^2} = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{l}{n}\right)^2}$$

Furthermore, with suitable choice of units for μ , K , and \hbar , the semi-major and semi-minor axes of the orbital ellipse can be expressed in terms of only the spectral indices:

$$a = n^2$$

$$b = n l$$

From this, we obtain the unitless radial turning points (periapsis r_p and apoapsis r_a) of the orbital ellipse (using the standard expression for elliptical orbits) strictly in terms of spectral indices:

$$r_{a,p} = a(1 \pm \epsilon)$$

$$= n^2(1 \pm \epsilon)$$

$$= n^2 \left(1 \pm \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{l}{n}\right)^2} \right)$$

6.4.2.2.1.2 Graphical Depiction of Elliptical Orbits in Terms of Spectral Indices

The following are graphical depictions of elliptical orbits in terms of the spectral indices n and l . The major axes of the ellipses are on the z axis, with the central-potential source at the focal point, which is in turn at the coordinate origin. The radial turning points are at the ellipse apoapsis and periapsis. The ellipse semi-major axis a and semi-minor axis b are defined in terms of the spectral indices, as described above. The following plots are for the range of spectral indices $n = 1 \dots 7$, $l = 1 \dots n - 1$.

$$n = 2, l = 1$$

6.4.2.2.1.3 Energy Accounting

In addition, we can express the radial-only energy spectral index N in terms of the spectral index n and the orbital ellipse eccentricity:

$$N = 2n\epsilon$$

This allows expression of the total energy in terms of the radial-only energy E_N and the orbital ellipse eccentricity:

$$E_N = -\frac{2\mu K^2}{\hbar^2 N^2} = -\frac{\mu K^2}{2\hbar^2(n^2 - l^2)} = -\frac{\mu K^2}{2\hbar^2 n^2 \left(1 - \frac{l^2}{n^2}\right)} = -\frac{\mu K^2}{2\hbar^2 n^2 \epsilon^2} = \frac{E_n}{\epsilon^2}$$

$$E_n = E_N \epsilon^2 = E_{n,l} \epsilon^2$$

With the total energy E_n being the sum of the radial (potential + kinetic) and the angular (kinetic only) energy, we obtain an expression for the angular kinetic energy E_l :

$$E_n = E_N \epsilon^2 = E_N + E_l$$

$$E_l = E_N (\epsilon^2 - 1)$$

$$= -\frac{l^2}{n^2} \cdot E_N$$

Given that E_N is a negative quantity, this is consistent with the angular kinetic energy E_l being a positive quantity.

6.4.2.2.1.4 Categories of Motion

We can conclude from the above characterizations of the motion that there are three broad categories of motion, where:

1. There is no angular momentum, and thus, motion consists entirely of radial oscillation (i.e., $L^2 = 0$).
2. The angular momentum is non-zero ($L^2 > 0$), wherein motion consists of both orbital (angular) motion and radial oscillation (the degree of radial oscillation being proportional to the eccentricity of the orbital ellipse).
3. The motion is entirely orbital, and there is no radial oscillation. In this case, all kinetic energy would be entirely due to orbital motion. However, in this case, the ellipse would have an eccentricity of 0, which would require that $l = n$. However, this condition would make the energy E_N undefined (due to $n^2 - l^2 = 0$ in the denominator of its definition).

Thus, we conclude that there are no orbits with zero eccentricity; instead, it is always true that $l \leq n - 1$.

6.4.2.2.1.5 $P_m(r)$ Extrema

We find the locations of the q extrema of $P_{m[n,l]}(r)$ by finding solutions to $\frac{dP_{m[n,l]}(r)}{dr} = 0$.

With $q \in \mathbb{z}$ and $2l \leq q \leq 2n$, the extrema of $P_{m[n,l]}(r)$ are found at:

$$r_{n,l,q} = \frac{N}{4} \left(N \pm \sqrt{4n^2 - q^2} \right)$$

These extrema will be useful for determination of radial scaling constants.

6.4.2.2.1.6 Radius Scaled to Orbital Ellipse in Terms of Spectral Indices

In the discussion of defining a radius scaling factor, it is worth noting that although, in the definition of $P_{mp}(r)$, the value of $P_p(r)$ can shift the maxima of $P_m(r)$, it does not shift the minima of $P_m(r)$ (because they are zeros of $P_m(r)$). This provides useful anchor points for shifting and sizing $P_m(r)$ (and $P_{mp}(r)$) to align (position and scale) the radial probability density of measurable presence to the orbital ellipse in terms of the spectral indices, as described above. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that the scaled radial probability density distribution of the canonical model (typically using the scaled radius $\rho = \frac{2Z}{a_0 n} \cdot r$) naturally aligns with the corresponding orbital ellipse described in this model in terms of the spectral indices. These considerations allow us to scale the radius to position and scale $P_m(r)$ of this model in a way that naturally corresponds to the radial probability density distribution of the canonical model.

What follows in this analysis will apply equally to both $P_m(r)$ and $P_{mp}(r)$, though the locations of maxima for the case $l = n - 1$ are different for $P_m(r)$ and $P_{mp}(r)$.

6.4.2.2.1.7 Scaled and Aligned To Dimensions and Radial Position of Orbital Ellipse

We will scale the radial dimension in terms of the periapsis and apoapsis of the orbital ellipse, given that the radial displacement oscillates between these two radial turning points. The approach is similar to that taken for scaling the displacement for the bouncing ball and harmonic oscillator, though this case differs somewhat in that radial motion is not symmetric between the radial turning points, and the radial oscillation takes place within the context of the elliptical orbit.

We can scale the radius to align with the radial position and dimensions of the elliptical orbit, in terms of spectral indices, by setting the orbital ellipse apoapsis $r_a = n^2(1 + \epsilon)$ equal to the outer radial turning point (obtained for the polynomial potential case $s = -1$) multiplied by a scaling constant σ :

$$r_a = \left(\frac{N}{\Xi} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sigma$$

$$n^2(1 + \epsilon) = \left(\frac{N}{\Xi} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sigma$$

$$n^2(1 + \epsilon) = \left(\frac{2n\epsilon}{\Xi}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sigma$$

$$r_a \cdot \sigma = \left(\frac{N}{\Xi}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2}$$

$$n^2(1 + \epsilon) \cdot \sigma = \left(\frac{N}{\Xi}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2}$$

$$n^2(1 + \epsilon) \cdot \sigma = \left(\frac{2n\epsilon}{\Xi}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2}$$

Solving for σ , we obtain:

$$\sigma = \frac{\Xi^2(1+\epsilon)}{2\epsilon^2}$$

$$\sigma = \frac{2\epsilon^2}{\Xi^2(1+\epsilon)}$$

We note that the units of σ are $\frac{1}{[length]}$.

We note that the units of σ are $[length]$.

Additionally, we can shift $P_m(r)$ from the origin by the magnitude of the periapsis,

$r_p = n^2(1 - \epsilon)$, so that the scaled radius is expressed as follows:

$$\rho = (r - r_p) \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma}$$

$$\rho = (r - r_p) \cdot \sigma$$

This scaling and shifting of the radius then positions $P_m(\rho)$ within the orbital ellipse. We see that ρ is a unitless quantity, considering the units of σ identified above.

6.4.2.2.1.8 Graphical Depiction of $P_m(\rho)$ Scaled to Orbital Ellipse

We now examine graphical depictions of $P_m(\rho)$, which are scaled and aligned to the orbital ellipse, plotted (in blue) against the corresponding radial probability density distributions of the canonical model (in Poupon mustard) using the dimensionless displacement $\rho = \frac{Z(r-r_p)}{a_0 \cdot \sigma}$ (scaled

in a way that is similar to $\rho = \frac{Zr}{a_0 n}$ of the canonical model) using the displacement $\rho = \frac{Z(r-r_p) \cdot \sigma}{a_0}$

(scaled in a way that is similar to that used for the one dimensional systems) for the range of spectral indices $n = 1 \dots 7$, $l = 0 \dots n - 1$:

$$n = 1, l = 0$$

$n = 2, l = 0..1$

$n = 3, l = 0..2$

$n = 4, l = 0..3$

$n = 5, l = 0..4$

$n = 6, l = 0..5$

$n = 7, l = 0..6$

6.4.2.2.1.9 Scaled to the Canonical Model Outer Minimum

We can further expand or shrink $P_m(\rho)$ by an additional (mathematically arbitrary) scaling factor f_σ , which we choose based on the relationship between the outer minimum of $P_m(r)$ and the outer minimum of the canonical model (the outer zero of the Laguerre polynomial).

There are two cases of the radial probability density distribution to consider for the purpose of determining f_σ in order to scale $P_m(\rho)$ to correspond to the canonical model:

- A. $l = n - 1$
- B. $l < n - 1$

In both cases, we have $(n - l)$ maxima and $(n - l - 1)$ minima. This excludes the minima at the turning points in this model and at $\rho = 0$ and $\rho = \infty$ in the canonical model.

In **case A**, there is a single maximum at $\rho = n^2$ (as there are no non-turning point minima), making this single maximum the only fixed reference point in the canonical model with which to align the radial distribution of this model. The corresponding maxima for $P_m(r)$ and $P_{mp}(r)$ can be determined numerically (though possibly also analytically, given that the relation $l = n - 1$ may simplify the derivative enough to analytically solve for the sole maximum).

Using the single maximum (at $\rho = n^2$) of the canonical solution and the corresponding single maximum (at r_{max}) of $P_m(r)$ and $P_{mp}(r)$, we define f_σ as the ratio of the differences of these two corresponding maxima locations with the periapsis r_p ($l = n - 1$):

$$f_\sigma = \frac{(n^2 - r_p)}{(r_{max} - r_p)}$$

$$f_\sigma = \frac{(r_{max} - r_p)}{(n^2 - r_p)}$$

In **case B**, there is at least one minimum. Given the advantageous property of the minima of $P_m(r)$ described above (i.e., they act as anchor points), we will align a minimum with the corresponding minimum in the canonical model. In particular, we choose the minimum closest to the orbital ellipse apoapsis¹ (rather than the one closest to the periapsis – though they are one and the same for $n - l = 2$), referring to this as the “apoapsis minimum.” The radial position of the apoapsis minimum for $P_m(r)$ is determined analytically. The corresponding radial position for the canonical model is one of the zeros of the Laguerre polynomial (obtained analytically).

Using the expression for the extrema of $P_m(r)$ obtained earlier, the apoapsis minimum $r_{\rho t}$ for $P_m(r)$ is obtained by setting $q = 2(n - 1)$ in that expression:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{\rho t} &= 2 \cdot \frac{N}{4} \left(N - \sqrt{4n^2 - q^2} \right) \\ &= 2n\epsilon \left(n\epsilon - \sqrt{2n - 1} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Using the apoapsis minimum for $P_m(\rho)$, defined as:

$$r_{\rho t \sigma} = r_{\rho t} \cdot \sigma + r_p$$

along with the apoapsis minimum $r_{\rho c}$ for the canonical solution (obtained analytically), we define f_σ as the ratio of the difference between these two corresponding minima locations and the periapsis (for $l < n - 1$):

$$\begin{aligned} f_\sigma &= \frac{(r_{\rho c} - r_p)}{(r_{\rho t \sigma} - r_p)} \\ f_\sigma &= \frac{(r_{\rho t \sigma} - r_p)}{(r_{\rho c} - r_p)} \end{aligned}$$

It should be noted that it is the ratio of differences between extrema and periapsis (not the origin) that aligns the radial distributions for this model and the canonical model. This somewhat remarkable finding suggests that the canonical model is inherently scaled to the size and radial position of the orbital ellipse (in terms of spectral indices).

This gives us a scaled radius of the form:

$$\rho = \frac{Z}{a_0} \cdot \frac{(r - r_p)}{f_\sigma \cdot \sigma}$$

$$\rho = \frac{Z}{a_0} \cdot (r - r_p) \cdot f_\sigma \cdot \sigma$$

¹ However, this process of alignment can be performed using any corresponding minima, including the periapsis minimum, or any minima between the periapsis and apoapsis minima. Minima are indicated in this model by the value of q chosen (e.g. $2[L+1]$, $2[L+2]$, ..., $2[n-1]$), and determined in the canonical model analytically. The choice of minimum determines where the radial density distributions of this model and the canonical model align best.

We use this definition of ρ for subsequent analysis of $P_p(r)$ and $P_{mp}(r)$, as well as for plots of the radial probability density distribution.

6.4.2.2.1.10 Graphical Depiction of $P_m(\rho)$ Scaled to Canonical Model Outer Minimum

We now examine graphical depictions of $P_m(\rho)$ – scaled to the outer minimum of the canonical model – plotted (in green) against the corresponding radial probability density distributions of the canonical model (in Poupon mustard) using the dimensionless displacement $\rho = \frac{Z(r-r_p)}{a_0 \cdot f_\sigma \cdot \sigma}$

(scaled in a way that is similar to $\rho = \frac{2Zr}{a_0 n}$ of the canonical model) using the displacement

$$\rho = \frac{Z(r-r_p) \cdot f_\sigma \cdot \sigma}{a_0} \text{ (scaled in a way that is similar to that used for the one dimensional systems) for}$$

the range of spectral indices $n = 1 \dots 7$, $l = 0 \dots n - 1$:

$$n = 1, l = 0$$

$$n = 2, l = 0 \dots 1$$

$$n = 3, l = 0 \dots 2$$

$$n = 4, l = 0 \dots 3$$

$$n = 5, l = 0 \dots 4$$

$n = 6, l = 0..5$

$n = 7, l = 0..6$

6.4.2.2.2 Form of $P_p(\rho)$

Starting with the assumption stated above that the probability of presence is inversely proportional to the velocity ($v_\rho = \frac{p_\rho}{\mu}$), we use the expression for the momentum in terms of spectral indices of the constants of motion to obtain:

$$P_p(\rho) \propto \frac{1}{v_\rho} = \frac{\mu}{\Xi \sqrt{\left| \frac{1}{p} \left(1 + \left[\frac{l}{\Xi} \right]^2 \frac{1}{p} \right) - \left[\frac{\Xi}{N} \right]^2 \right|}}$$

6.4.2.2.2.1 Turning Points

Following the method used with polynomial potentials to obtain the radial turning points, we find values for r which make the radial momentum $p_r = 0$:

$$p_r = \Xi \sqrt{\left| \frac{1}{r} \left(1 + \left[\frac{l}{\Xi} \right]^2 \frac{1}{r} \right) - \left[\frac{\Xi}{N} \right]^2 \right|} = 0$$

This yields the two dimensional radial turning points (apoapsis r_a and periapsis r_p of the elliptical orbit):

$$r_{a,p} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{N}{\epsilon} \right)^2 \cdot \left[1 \pm \sqrt{1 + 4 \left(\frac{l}{N} \right)^2} \right]$$

These dimensional turning points $r_{a,p}$ are related to the non-dimensional turning points $r_{a,p}$ (in terms of spectral indices) derived above in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{a,p} &= r_{a,p} \cdot 2\epsilon \cdot \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \\ &= n^2 (1 \pm \epsilon) \cdot 2\epsilon \cdot \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \\ &= n \cdot N \cdot (1 \pm \epsilon) \cdot \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \end{aligned}$$

6.4.2.2.2 Graphical Depiction

The following are graphical depictions of $P_p(\rho)$ for the range of spectral indices $n = 1 \dots 7$, $l = 0 \dots n - 1$:

$n = 1, l = 0$

$n = 2, l = 0 \dots 1$

$n = 3, l = 0 \dots 2$

$n = 4, l = 0 \dots 3$

$n = 5, l = 0..4$

$n = 6, l = 0..5$

$n = 7, l = 0..6$

6.4.2.2.3 Form of $P_{mp}(\rho)$

The expression for $P_{mp}(\rho)$ is the simple algebraic product:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{mp}(\rho) &= P_m(\rho) \cdot P_p(\rho) \\
 &= \frac{\cos^2[\pi \Xi \rho p]}{p_\rho} \\
 &= \frac{\cos^2 \left[\pi \Xi \rho \sqrt{\left| \frac{1}{\rho} \left(1 + \left[\frac{l}{\Xi} \right]^2 \frac{1}{\rho} \right) - \left[\frac{\Xi}{N} \right]^2} \right]}{\Xi \sqrt{\left| \frac{1}{\rho} \left(1 + \left[\frac{l}{\Xi} \right]^2 \frac{1}{\rho} \right) - \left[\frac{\Xi}{N} \right]^2} \right]}
 \end{aligned}$$

6.4.2.2.3.1 Graphical Depiction

We now examine graphical depictions of $P_{mp}(\rho)$ plotted (in blue) against the corresponding radial probability density distributions of the canonical model (in Poupon mustard).

This set of plots depicts $P_{mp}(\rho)$ with ρ scaled and aligned with the orbital ellipse for the range of spectral indices $n = 1 \dots 7$, $l = 0 \dots n - 1$:

$n = 1, l = 0$

$n = 2, l = 0 \dots 1$

$n = 3, l = 0 \dots 2$

$n = 4, l = 0 \dots 3$

$n = 5, l = 0 \dots 4$

$n = 6, l = 0 \dots 5$

$n = 7, l = 0..6$

This set of plots depicts $P_{mp}(\rho)$ as above except with ρ additionally scaled to the outer minimum of the canonical model, using the method described above, for the range of spectral indices $n = 1..7, l = 0..n - 1$:

$n = 1, l = 0$

$n = 2, l = 0..1$

$n = 3, l = 0..2$

$n = 4, l = 0..3$

$n = 5, l = 0 \dots 4$

$n = 6, l = 0 \dots 5$

$n = 7, l = 0 \dots 6$

6.4.2.2.4 Correspondence to Canonical Quantum Solution

In broad terms, this model is similar to the canonical quantum solution. A brief examination of series expansions of the two solutions reveals a similarity in analytical expression that underlies their similar characteristics.

6.4.2.2.4.1 Mathematical Similarity to Canonical Quantum Solution

There is a degree of mathematical similarity between the analytical description of the system in this model and in the canonical model.

The series expansion of $P_m(r)$ is of the order:

$$\cos^2 \left[\pi \Xi \rho \sqrt{\frac{1}{\rho} \left(1 + \left[\frac{l}{\Xi} \right]^2 \frac{1}{\rho} \right) - \left[\frac{\Xi}{N} \right]^2} \right] \simeq \cos^2(\sqrt{\rho})$$

$$\begin{aligned}\sqrt{\cos^2(\sqrt{\rho})} &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \cdot \frac{\rho^k}{(2k)!} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\rho)^k}{(2k)!}\end{aligned}$$

Recalling that:

$$P_p(\rho) \propto \frac{\mu}{\Xi \sqrt{\frac{1}{\rho} \left(1 + \left[\frac{l}{\Xi} \right]^2 \frac{1}{\rho} \right) - \left[\frac{\Xi}{N} \right]^2}}$$

The series expansion of $P_p(r)$ is of the order:

$$\simeq \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\Xi^2}{N^2} \right)^{\frac{-1}{2(l+2k)}}}{\Xi r} \cdot \binom{-\frac{1}{2}}{k} \cdot l^{2k} \right]$$

The series expansion of the canonical description is of the order (with $L_{n+1}^{2l+1}(\rho)$ being the Associated Laguerre polynomials):

$$\begin{aligned}R_{nl}(\rho) &= A_{nl} \cdot L_{n+1}^{2l+1}(\rho) \cdot \rho^l \cdot e^{-\frac{\rho}{2}} \\ &\simeq \left(\sim \rho^{n-l-1} \right) \cdot \rho^l \cdot \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\rho)^k}{k!} \\ &\simeq \sim \rho^{n-1} \cdot \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\rho)^k}{k!}\end{aligned}$$

6.4.3 Angular Probability Density Distribution $P_{mp}(\theta, \phi)$

The method of describing the probability of measurability that was applied to linear dimensions will now be applied to the polar (θ) and azimuthal (ϕ) angular dimensions in spherical coordinates in the description of the central potential system. Just as spectral indices were found from analysis of the radial dimension (n and l), so we will find spectral indices for the angular dimensions (l_θ and l_ϕ).

In what follows, ξ represents both angular dimensions (θ, ϕ), and l_ξ represents their respective angular momentum spectral indices (l_θ, l_ϕ).

In the $\frac{K}{r}$ central-potential system, where angular momentum is a constant of the motion, the relationship between constant angular momentum and angular displacement parallels the relationship between constant linear momentum and linear displacement examined earlier in the Particle-in-a-Box (PIB) system. This is to be expected because, in the PIB system, there is no potential along the linear displacement x (i.e., no force), and in this system, there is no angular

potential (i.e., no torque). The only essential difference between the two is that, for the PIB system, a constant linear momentum is exhibited along a dimensional linear displacement, while for the angular probability density of measurability, a constant angular momentum is exhibited along a non-dimensional angular displacement. In fact, their phase-space descriptions are the same, while their respective configuration space descriptions differ only by a factor of π for the displacement. The angular momentum analog of the PIB boundaries at $x = \pm L$ are the angular boundaries at $\xi = \pm \pi$ where $P_m(\xi)$ repeats (i.e., exhibits continuity).

For many of the plots that follow, we choose $l_\xi = 2$ (and thus l_θ and l_ϕ) to illustrate some of the essential aspects of $P_m(\alpha)$ and $P_m(\xi)$, though the results are general and hold true for all values of l_ξ ($l_\xi \in \mathbb{Z}, l_\xi > 0$).

6.4.3.1 In Phase Space

We first derive the expression for $P_m(\alpha)$ in phase space. This result, along with spectral indices for the constants of motion derived from imposing boundary conditions, will subsequently be used to derive $P_m(\xi)$ in configuration space.

6.4.3.1.1 Form of $P_m(\alpha)$

The form of the angular probability density distribution $P_m(\alpha)$ in phase space is identical to the form of $P_m(\alpha)$ for the PIB system, with l_ξ replacing q as the spectral index, and a factor of $\frac{1}{2}$ to reflect that the path is only half the total cycle, using the notational simplification introduced earlier (where $\Phi_q = \mathbb{P}(q) \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}$):

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 \left[\frac{1}{2} \pi \cdot l_\xi \cdot \cos(\alpha) - \Phi_\xi \right]$$

6.4.3.1.2 Graphical Depiction

In the plots that follow, those on the left have a phase angle of 0, while those on the right have a phase angle of $\frac{\pi}{2}$.

6.4.3.2 In Configuration Space

As we will see, angular motion in spherical coordinates can be viewed as composed of both:

1. Angular motion **through** the polar axis (described by θ) and its resulting angular momentum l_θ . It is noteworthy that the direction (i.e., ϕ component) of the angular momentum vector corresponding to this angular motion is indeterminate.
2. Angular motion **about** the polar axis (described by ϕ) and its resulting angular momentum l_ϕ . The direction of the angular momentum vector corresponding to this angular motion is along the z axis.

6.4.3.2.1 Form of $P_m(\theta)$ and $P_m(\phi)$

The expression for the angular variation in the probability density distribution as a function of angular momentum with respect to angular displacement is identical to the form of $P_m(x)$ for the PIB system defined in 5.1.4.5 (given that $L = \pi$, where L is the displacement boundary of the PIB system):

$$P_m(\xi) = \cos^2 \left[\frac{\pi \cdot l_\xi \cdot \xi}{\pi} - \Phi_\xi \right]$$

$$= \cos^2 \left[l_\xi \cdot \xi - \Phi_\xi \right]$$

6.4.3.2.2 Graphical Depiction

A graphical depiction of $P_m(\xi)$ in angular configuration space is as follows:

Graphical depiction of $P_m(\xi)$ in the plane in which the subtended angle resides is shown in two forms in the following plots, showing the probability of measurability as it varies with angular position:

- In the first form, the probability density distributions are depicted in a polar plot, with distance from the origin to a point on the curve indicating probability density $P_m(\xi)$ at that angular displacement ($0 < P_m(\xi) < 1$).

- In the second form, probability density distributions are depicted in a density plot with shading indicating probability density at each angular displacement (white indicating $P_m(\xi) = 0$, blue indicating $P_m(\xi) = 1$, shading indicating $0 < P_m(\xi) < 1$).

The angular variation in $P_m(\xi)$ is depicted in a polar plot:

The angular variation in $P_m(\xi)$ is depicted in a density plot:

6.4.3.2.3 Polar and Azimuthal Angular Motion

Beyond this point in the discussion, the analysis will bifurcate somewhat between angular position for angular motion *through* the polar axis ($\xi \rightarrow \theta$) and angular position for angular motion *about* the polar axis ($\xi \rightarrow \phi$). The different paths of analysis emerge from the different ways angular position is described for the two dimensions.

6.4.3.2.3.1 Polar Angular Motion Through the Polar Axis: $P_m(\theta)$

When we describe polar angular motion through the polar axis, the value of ϕ is indeterminate, so the plots are rotationally symmetric about the polar axis. It is a consequence of the

indeterminate value of ϕ that the direction of the corresponding angular momentum vector is also indeterminate.

The expression for the polar angular probability of measurability follows the general form for angular measure presented above (for ξ):

$$P_m(\theta) = \cos^2[l_\theta \theta - \Phi_\theta]$$

In this example, we see the angular probability density distribution about an axis parallel to the X-Y plane (including the phase-shifted plot):

$$\Phi_\theta = 0$$

$$\Phi_\theta = 1$$

As there is no preferred value of ϕ , the probability density distribution is represented by the surface of revolution about the polar axis (i.e., $0 \leq \phi \leq 2\pi$):

$$\Phi_\theta = 0$$

$$\Phi_\theta = 1$$

$$\Phi_{\theta} = 0$$

$$\Phi_{\theta} = 1$$

The same information is conveyed in the following density plot, with the color shading interpreted in the same way as described for the density plots above:

$$\Phi_{\theta} = 0$$

$$\Phi_{\theta} = 1$$

6.4.3.2.3.2 Azimuthal Angular Motion About the Polar Axis: $P_m(\phi)$

When we describe azimuthal angular motion about the polar axis, we do not specify the plane in which the angular motion occurs; thus, the plots are in planes parallel to the plane $z = 0$, translated along the Z axis.

The expression for the azimuthal angular probability of measurability follows the general form for angular measure presented above (for ξ):

$$P_m(\phi) = \cos^2[l_{\phi}\phi - \Phi_{\phi}]$$

In this example, we see the angular probability density distribution about the Z axis in the plane $z = 0$:

$$\Phi_{\phi} = 0$$

$$\Phi_{\phi} = 1$$

As there is no preferred position on the z axis, the probability density distribution is represented by the surface of translation along the polar axis:

$$\Phi_{\phi} = 0$$

$$\Phi_{\phi} = 1$$

$$\Phi_{\phi} = 0$$

$$\Phi_{\phi} = 1$$

The same information is conveyed in the following density plot, with the color shading interpreted in the same way as described for the density plots above:

$$\Phi_\phi = 0$$

$$\Phi_\phi = 1$$

6.4.3.2.3.3 Combining $P_m(\theta)$ and $P_m(\phi)$ to give $P_m(\theta, \phi)$

We define the solid angular probability density distribution of measurability $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ as the simple algebraic product of the two angular values $P_m(\theta)$ and $P_m(\phi)$:

$$P_m(\theta, \phi) = P_m(\theta) \cdot P_m(\phi)$$

This is depicted graphically as (using the same values for $l_\theta, \Phi_\theta, l_\phi, \Phi_\phi$ as in the plots above):

6.4.3.2.4 Comparing $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ to $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$

At this point in the analysis, we now have a way to describe the angular probability density distribution for arbitrary combinations of the polar (l_θ, Φ_θ) and azimuthal (l_ϕ, Φ_ϕ) spectral indices and phase angles. As will be seen in later analysis, not all combinations of these spectral indices conform to physical constraints of the central-potential system. Imposing those

constraints will restrict the combinations of spectral indices and the polar angle domain that are used in describing this system.

We will now compare the analytical forms and graphical depictions of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ and $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$.

6.4.3.2.4.1 Analytical Comparison of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ with Spherical Harmonics $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$

Adopting a convention of referring to the θ portion of the spherical harmonics $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$ as $Y_l^m(\theta)$ and the ϕ portion as $Y_l^m(\phi)$, inspection shows that the form of $P_m(\phi)$ is identical to the real part of $Y_l^m(\phi)$, with the effect that $P_m(\phi)$ yields the same azimuthal probability (of measurability) density distribution as the real part of $Y_l^m(\phi)$. Inspection of the polar angular probability density distribution $P_m(\theta)$ readily shows that when $\cos\left[l_\theta \theta + \Phi_\theta \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$ (upon which the definition of $P_m(\theta)$ is based) is trigonometrically expanded, these expansions yield non-linear trigonometric polynomials exhibiting structural similarity to the (non-linear) trigonometric polynomial portion of $Y_l^m(\theta)$. In addition, we see that $Y_l^m(\theta)$ contains the additional factor:

$$T(\theta) = \frac{\sin[\theta]^{(|m|-1+\delta_m)}}{2^{(l-|m|-\delta_m)}} \quad (1)$$

This factor has the effect of shifting the angular density lobes of $Y_l^m(\theta)$ away from the poles and toward the equator and “compressing” them into an equatorial toroidal region, with greater effect for higher values of $|m|$. We will see the same effect achieved — by different means — in the definitions of $P_m(\theta)$ and $P_p(\theta)$ that result from the effective polar angular domain of a declined elliptical orbit plane. A comparison of the analytical forms of $Y_l^m(\theta)$ and $P_m(\theta)$ can be found in appendix A.1. A tabulation of the quotient $\frac{Y_l^m(\theta)}{\sqrt{P_m(\theta)}}$ is provided in appendix A.2.

6.4.3.2.4.2 Graphical Comparison of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ with Spherical Harmonics $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$

When we compare the graphical representation of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ to that of $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$, we see two aspects in which they differ, with these differences varying in relation to the azimuthal quantum number m (and, correspondingly, the spectral index l_ϕ). One aspect is – with increasing values of $|m|$ – the “compression” of probability lobes toward the equator (and away from the poles), as mentioned above. This is caused by the factor $T(\theta)$ identified above. The other aspect is – with decreasing values of $|m|$ – a “thinning” of probability density in the equatorial region relative to a “thickening” of probability density toward the poles. These aspects are illustrated in appendix D.

6.4.3.2.5 Relationship of l_ϕ , Φ_ϕ to Canonical Azimuthal Quantum Number m

From the above comparison of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ and $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$, it is evident that there is a relationship between the canonical azimuthal quantum number m and the spectral index l_ϕ and the phase angle Φ_ϕ . The precise relationships among these are as follows:

$$l_\phi = |m|$$

$$\Phi_\phi = 1 - \delta_{(|m|+m)}$$

Additionally, this implies:

$$\delta_{l_\phi} = \delta_m$$

Where appropriate, we will hereafter use the spectral index m in place of l_ϕ and Φ_ϕ , with it being understood that Φ_ϕ is asserted by the sign of m (in some cases, use of l_ϕ and Φ_ϕ will still be warranted to refer to their specific roles as distinct from the role of m).

N.B. - Use of the spectral index m is not to be confused with use of the letter “m” in the role of the subscript “m” in $P_m(\)$, which indicates measurability.

6.4.3.2.6 Constraints Arising from Physical Aspects of the System

The central-potential system is not only characterized by the constant energy $E_{n,l}$ and constant total angular momentum l (established in section 6.4.2 describing radial motion), but also by a constant orientation of the orbital ellipse plane – relative only to the polar axis – in configuration space. This constant orientation is expressed as a constant angular declination of the total angular momentum vector of the system from the polar axis at an angle $\theta = \tau_l$. We do not specify an azimuthal orientation of this vector (it is not indicated by the system and thus is indeterminate). This angle of declination is readily expressed in terms of the ratio of the azimuthal spectral index to the spectral index of the total angular momentum². As the total angular momentum vector is orthogonal to the plane of the elliptical orbit, this orbital plane also has a correspondingly constant orientation w.r.t. the polar axis at declination angle $\theta = \tau$ (where $\tau \perp \tau_l$ and τ is the angle between the ellipse major axis and the polar axis, with the ellipse minor axis being parallel to the plane $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$).

As we will see, the declination of the orbital plane constrains the polar angle domain, and the polar angular velocity of the particle in the elliptical orbit yields a polar angular probability of presence that modulates the total polar angular probability density of measurable presence in such a way that the effects noted in 6.4.3.2.4.1 are manifest in this model as well.

² We will see that the spectral index of the total angular momentum is derived from the radial spectral index l and the angular spectral indices l^θ and l^ϕ .

The declination of the orbital plane manifestly imposes a constraint on the polar angular domain, evident in the geometry of the system, as seen in the following plots depicting ellipses (doubly degenerate w.r.t. polar axis), with ellipse major axes declined by an angle τ (and $\pi - \tau$) from the polar axis (and ellipse minor axes parallel to the plane $z = 0$). Plot (a) depicts these ellipses viewed obliquely. Plot (b) is simply plot (a) viewed from the side (i.e. from the +X direction), showing the effective angular domain $0 + \tau \leq \theta \leq \pi - \tau$ between the upper and lower ellipses. Plot (c) depicts the conical surface of revolution of the orbital ellipse major axes, as well as the surface of revolution of the ellipses — both about the polar axis — which illustrate the azimuthal indeterminacy of the system.

6.4.3.2.6.1 Combinations of l_θ , Φ_θ , l_ϕ and Φ_ϕ Prohibited by Finite Spatial Volume Requirement

There are certain combinations of l_θ , Φ_θ , l_ϕ and Φ_ϕ that, when taken together with radial bounds (corresponding to orbital ellipse dimensions), fail to contain total probability density in a finite spatial volume, and so are not permitted. The rules identifying these prohibited combinations are:

- The value l_θ can never be zero when

6.4.3.2.6.2 Constant Angular Momentum Magnitude

One clear constraint on the combination of polar (l_θ) and azimuthal (l_ϕ) angular momentum spectral indices is that the constant angular momentum of the system requires that these two values combine (perhaps additively) to yield a constant value. If we consider the case of when the orbital ellipse has a zero declination angle ($\tau = 0$), then all the angular momentum of the system must be embodied in the value of l_θ . This means that when $l_\theta = l$, then it must be that $l_\phi = 0$. Furthermore, when $l_\theta = l$, the phase angle value must be $\Phi_\theta = 1$ in order for the probability of measurability at the orbital ellipse extrema (periapsis and apoapsis) to be non-zero.

We put forth the following conjectures (for which we expect physical justification can be found by further analysis):

- The total measurable angular momentum L_m of the system is a constant and is related to both the constant angular momentum l of the radial solution and the angular spectral indices, expressed in the following relationship (making use of expressions for l_ϕ and δ_{l_ϕ} defined in 6.4.3.2.5):

$$\begin{aligned} L_m &= l_\theta + l_\phi + \delta_{l_\phi} \\ &= l_\theta + |m| + \delta_m \\ &= l + 1 \end{aligned}$$

- The total angular momentum of the system is:

$$\begin{aligned} L &= \sqrt{l \cdot L_m} \\ &= \sqrt{l \cdot (l + 1)} \end{aligned}$$

6.4.3.2.6.3 Constant Orbital Ellipse Declination from Polar Axis

The following relationships characterize the declination of the angular momentum vector at angle $\theta = \tau_l$ and consequently the orbital ellipse plane at angle $\theta = \tau$, in terms of the total angular momentum L and the azimuthal spectral index l_ϕ :

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_l &= \arccos \left[\frac{l_\phi}{L} \right] \\ &= \arccos \left[\frac{|m|}{L} \right] \\ \\ \tau &= \frac{\pi}{2} - \tau_l \\ &= \arcsin \left[\frac{|m|}{L} \right] \end{aligned}$$

6.4.3.2.6.4 Polar Angular Domain Constraint

Upon closer scrutiny, we see that although the constraint on the polar angular domain seems clearly related to the angle of declination τ of the orbital ellipse plane, by considering the similarity between the behavior of the probability of measurability for angular measure in this system and for linear measure in the PIB system, we recognize that the angular boundaries within which $P_m(\theta)$ varies are *not* the angular positions of the outer maxima of $P_m(\theta)$, but instead we put forth the conjecture that the boundaries are the angular positions $0 + \tau_{env}$ and $\pi - \tau_{env}$, where (it is expected that this can be justified by more careful physical considerations in subsequent analysis):

$$\tau_{env} = \arcsin \left[\frac{|m|-1}{L} \right]$$

It is noteworthy that this expression shows the same dependence on $(|m| - 1)$ as does the factor $T(\theta)$ in the earlier analytical comparison of $P_m(\theta)$ with $Y_l^m(\theta)$ in section 6.4.3.2.4.1.

More generally (to handle the case where $m = 0$), we have:

$$\tau_{env} = \arcsin\left[\frac{l-l_\theta}{L}\right]$$

Therefore, the relationship between the constrained polar angle θ_{eff} and the polar angle θ is:

$$\theta_{eff}(\theta) = (\theta - \tau_{env}) \cdot \frac{\pi}{(\pi - 2\tau_{env})}$$

This achieves alignment of the polar angular probability density (measurability and presence) distributions to the polar angular range of the (doubly degenerate) declined orbital ellipse planes. Upon inspection, we see that this amounts to alignment of the polar angular domain (position and scale) with the polar angular limits of the declined orbital ellipse, which is analogous to alignment of the radial domain (position and scale) to the radial limits of the orbital ellipse seen earlier.

6.4.3.2.7 Resulting Rules for Composition of $P_m(\theta)$, $P_m(\phi)$, $P_m(\theta, \phi)$

We will now employ the spectral indices for angular measure and their associated ranges of values customarily used in the canonical model (where l is the orbital angular momentum spectral index and m is the azimuthal angular momentum spectral index), constrained by the relationship, which we recall from above in 6.4.3.2.6.2:

$$l_\theta + |m| + \delta_m = l + 1$$

Using this, we define the following expressions for the composition of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$:

$$\begin{aligned}\sqrt{P_m(\theta)} &\equiv \cos\left[l_\theta\theta + (1 - \delta_m) \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}\right] \\ \sqrt{P_m(\phi)} &\equiv \cos\left[|m|\phi + (1 - \delta_{(|m|+m)}) \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}\right] \\ \sqrt{P_m(\theta, \phi)} &\equiv \sqrt{P_m(\theta)} \cdot \sqrt{P_m(\phi)}\end{aligned}$$

A graphical illustration of this composition (for $0 \leq l_\theta \leq 6$ and $-l_\theta \leq m \leq l_\theta$) is tabulated in appendix B.

6.4.3.2.8 Angular Probability of Presence

As with the 1-dimensional systems examined earlier — wherein the probability of presence was determined by the expression for particle speed (momentum) along the trajectory in terms of the constants of the motion (in the form of spectral index values obtained from boundary conditions) — so too is the angular probability of presence determined by the expression for angular speed

along the declined elliptical trajectory in terms of the constant angular momentum and elliptical orbit plane polar angular orientation (declination), in the form of the spectral indices l , l_θ and m .

In general, the probability of presence along an elliptical trajectory is the reciprocal of the speed along that trajectory. Specifically, the angular probability of presence along that trajectory is the reciprocal of the angular (not radial, not tangential) speed along that trajectory. The polar and azimuthal angular speeds along the trajectory are determined by analysis of the parallel projections of the declined orbital ellipse onto the $\phi = 0$ and $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$ planes, respectively. It is important to note that the polar angular domain is “compressed” within an envelope confined by the conical surface of revolution of the major axis of the orbital ellipses declined by the angle τ from the polar axis. We also make the simplifying assumption that polar angular probability of presence might appreciably change with increasing declination of the elliptical orbit plane; however, for the first approximation we assume that it is the same for any degree of declination. It is not clear that a more accurate treatment would yield an appreciably different (more or less accurate) probability density distribution.

6.4.3.2.8.1 Probability of Azimuthal Angular Presence

Because the azimuthal (ϕ) orientation of the elliptical orbit major axis (at any degree of declination) is indeterminate, the azimuthal angular locations of apoapsis and periapsis – and the accompanying different probabilities of presence at and between them – are also indeterminate. This results in the azimuthal angular probability of presence being effectively uniformly 1 (i.e., as the azimuthal orientation is indeterminate, any orientation is equally probable, and thus, presence at any azimuthal angle is equally probable).

This can be visualized using the following plots for various degrees of elliptical orbit plane declination from the polar axis:

Orbital Ellipse Declined from Polar (z) Axis (n=7, l=6)
 Periapsis=(0, 0, ±23.7611), Apoapsis=(0, 0, ±74.2389, →Z=65.8057, →XY=34.3659)
 a=49.0, b=42.0, e=0.515079, ppu(n=7,l=6,m=-3), pbs=0, Vpt=, ViewPoint→{1.3,-2.4,2}
 Lvec=ArcCos[Abs[MM]/Sqrt[LL*(LL + 1)]]
 Apex Angles: Lvec(θ=0.346805+Pi), OrbitalPlaneDeclination(θ=-0.153195+Pi)

Orbital Ellipse Declined from Polar (z) Axis (n=7, l=6)
 Periapsis=(0, 0, ±23.7611), Apoapsis=(0, 0, ±74.2389, →Z=65.8057, →XY=34.3659)
 a=49.0, b=42.0, e=0.515079, ppu(n=7,l=6,m=-3), pbs=0, Vpt=, ViewPoint→{1.3,-2.4,2}
 Lvec=ArcCos[Abs[MM]/Sqrt[LL*(LL + 1)]]
 Apex Angles: Lvec(θ=0.346805+Pi), OrbitalPlaneDeclination(θ=-0.153195+Pi)

Orbital Ellipse Declined from Polar (z) Axis (n=7, l=6)
 Periapsis=(0, 0, ±23.7611), Apoapsis=(0, 0, ±74.2389, →Z=28.0597, →XY=68.7318)
 a=49.0, b=42.0, e=0.515079, ppu(n=7,l=6,m=-6), pbs=0, Vpt=, ViewPoint→{1.3,-2.4,2}
 Lvec=ArcCos[Abs[MM]/Sqrt[LL*(LL + 1)]]
 Apex Angles: Lvec(θ=0.123376+Pi), OrbitalPlaneDeclination(θ=-0.376624+Pi)

Orbital Ellipse Declined from Polar (z) Axis (n=7, l=6)
 Periapsis=(0, 0, ±23.7611), Apoapsis=(0, 0, ±74.2389, →Z=28.0597, →XY=68.7318)
 a=49.0, b=42.0, e=0.515079, ppu(n=7,l=6,m=-6), pbs=0, Vpt=, ViewPoint→{1.3,-2.4,2}
 Lvec=ArcCos[Abs[MM]/Sqrt[LL*(LL + 1)]]
 Apex Angles: Lvec(θ=0.123376+Pi), OrbitalPlaneDeclination(θ=-0.376624+Pi)

This indeterminacy of the azimuthal orientation of the orbital ellipse major axis should not be understood as axial or apsidal precession of the ellipse but instead could be understood as representing the infinite degeneracy of azimuthal orientation (as opposed to the finite, double degeneracy of polar orientation) of the orbital ellipse.

Therefore, for $P_p(\phi)$ we simply have:

$$P_p(\phi) = 1$$

6.4.3.2.8.2 Probability of Polar Angular Presence

To derive the probability of polar angular presence $P_p(\theta)$, we consider the physics of angular speed in an elliptical orbit, as well as the consequence of the declination of the plane of this orbit from the polar axis with respect to polar angular speed and the constrained polar angle domain.

The probability of polar angular presence is a result of two aspects of orbital motion:

1. The probability of presence along the elliptical orbit trajectory, which is the reciprocal of the polar angular speed component of the particle's tangential speed along the elliptical orbit trajectory, gives the polar probability of presence along the elliptical orbit trajectory. This is the parallel projection of the angular speed along the elliptical orbit onto the plane $\phi = 0$.
2. The declination of the elliptical orbit plane from the polar axis, which defines a polar angular "envelope" about the equatorial plane. This constitutes the effective polar angular domain. We will align (polar angular position and scale) the polar angular probability density distribution with this envelope of elliptical orbit plane declination.

6.4.3.2.8.3 Probability of Presence Along Elliptical Orbit Trajectory

With the probability of presence along the elliptical trajectory taken to be inversely proportional to the angular (not tangential) velocity along that trajectory, it is thus greatest at apoapsis and least (though never zero) at periapsis.

The angular velocity along the elliptical orbit is a function of the tangential (v_t) and radial (v_r) velocities:

$$v_\theta = \sqrt{v_t^2 - v_r^2}$$

These velocities, given in terms of the polar angle θ , the angular momentum spectral index l and the orbital eccentricity ϵ , are:

$$v_t = \sqrt{\frac{1+2\epsilon\cos[\theta]+\epsilon^2}{l^2}}$$

$$v_r = \frac{\epsilon\sin[\theta]}{l}$$

which gives us for the angular velocity:

$$\begin{aligned} v_\theta &= \sqrt{\frac{1+2\epsilon\cos[\theta]+\epsilon^2}{l^2} - \left(\frac{\epsilon\sin[\theta]}{l}\right)^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{1+2\epsilon\cos[\theta]+\epsilon^2}{l^2} - \frac{\epsilon^2(1-\cos^2[\theta])}{l^2}} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{1+2\epsilon\cos[\theta]+\epsilon^2\cos^2[\theta]}{l^2}} \\ &= \frac{(1+\epsilon\cos[\theta])}{l} \end{aligned}$$

Note that in our convention, for an elliptical orbit with major axis aligned on the polar axis and apoapsis occurring at $\theta = 0$, the orbital ellipse is rotated by π ; thus, we substitute $[\theta \pm \pi]$ for θ , giving:

$$v_\theta = \frac{(1-\epsilon\cos[\theta])}{l}$$

The probability of presence along the elliptical orbit trajectory as a function of polar angle then amounts to:

$$P_p(\theta) \propto \frac{1}{v_\theta}$$

$$P_p(\theta) \propto \frac{l}{(1-\epsilon \cdot \cos[\theta])}$$

Given the expression for the radial distance to each point on the orbital ellipse from the focal point at which the source of the central potential is located:

$$r_\theta = \frac{a(1-\epsilon^2)}{(1+\epsilon \cos[\theta])}$$

we note incidentally that the product of v_θ and r_θ yields the constant angular momentum of the system, as would be expected:

$$v_\theta \cdot r_\theta = \frac{(1+\epsilon \cdot \cos[\theta])}{l} \cdot \frac{a(1-\epsilon^2)}{(1+\epsilon \cos[\theta])}$$

$$= \frac{n^2 \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{l^2}{n^2}\right)\right)}{l}$$

$$= l$$

6.4.3.2.8.4 Resulting Polar Angular Probability of Presence $P_p'(\theta)$

We propose the following simple expression for polar probability of presence for an orbital plane at zero declination from the polar axis using the expression for the probability of presence along the elliptical orbit trajectory derived above (this is an admittedly simplistic first approximation, as it does not take into account the effect of orbital plane declination on effective polar angular velocity — subsequent analysis must be performed to determine the actual dependence of $P_p(\theta)$ on τ):

For $(l - |m|) > 1$:

$$P_p'(\theta) = \frac{l}{(1-\epsilon \cdot \cos[\theta])} + \frac{l}{(1-\epsilon \cdot \cos[\theta-\pi])}$$

$$= \frac{l}{(1-\epsilon \cdot \cos[\theta])} + \frac{l}{(1+\epsilon \cdot \cos[\theta])}$$

$$= \frac{2l}{(1-\epsilon^2 \cdot \cos^2[\theta])}$$

For $(l - |m|) \leq 1$:

$$P_p'(\theta) = 1$$

These relations can be expressed more compactly by defining \mathfrak{n} using the Iverson bracket (asserting – as 1 or 0, respectively – whether or not the number of nodes in $P_m(\theta)$ is > 1):

$$\mathfrak{n} = [(l - |m|) > 1]$$

Allowing us to write $P_p'(\theta)$ as:

$$P_p'(\theta) = \mathfrak{n} \cdot \frac{2l}{(1-\epsilon^2 \cdot \cos^2[\theta])} + \delta_{\mathfrak{n}}$$

This expression exhibits lower probability (due to higher angular speed) at periapsis and higher probability (due to lower angular speed) at apoapsis, which are consistent with the properties of the canonical model examined in section 6.4.3.2.4.2.

6.4.3.2.9 Resulting $P_m(\theta_{eff})$ Within Declined Orbital Plane Envelope

Now, expressing $P_m(\theta)$ in terms of the constrained polar angular domain θ_{eff} defined above, we have the expression for the polar angular probability density of measurability within the polar angular envelope:

$$P_m(\theta_{eff}) = \cos^2[l\theta_{eff} - \Phi_{\theta}]$$

6.4.3.2.10 $P_p'(\theta_{eff})$ For Declined Orbital Plane

Now, expressing $P_p'(\theta)$ in terms of the constrained polar angular domain θ_{eff} defined above, we have the following form for the polar angular probability density of presence within the polar angular envelope:

$$P_p'(\theta_{eff}) = \mathfrak{n} \cdot \frac{2l}{(1-\epsilon^2 \cdot \cos^2[\theta_{eff}])} + \delta_{\mathfrak{n}}$$

6.4.3.2.10.1 Graphical Depiction of $P_p'(\theta_{eff})$

In the following, for $n = 7, l = 5, m = 0 \dots - 5$, plots **(a)** show $P_m(\theta)$ while plots **(b)** show $P_m(\theta_{eff})$ in solid blue, $P_p(\theta_{eff})$ and $P_p(\theta_{eff} - \pi)$ in solid orange, $P_p'(\theta_{eff})$ in solid red, $P_{mp}(\theta_{eff})$ in dashed purple and the canonical probability distribution $Y_l^m(\theta)$ in dashed green:

(a)
For $n = 7, l = 5, m = 0$:

(b)

For $n = 7, l = 5, m = -1$:

For $n = 7, l = 5, m = -2$:

For $n = 7, l = 5, m = -3$:

For $n = 7, l = 5, m = -4$:

For $n = 7, l = 5, m = -5$:

6.4.3.2.10.2 Refinement of $P_p^{-1}(\theta_{eff})$

It is possible that further refinements of $P_p^{-1}(\theta_{eff})$ are needed, such as accounting for geometric effects on the variation of probability of presence with polar angle for the declined orbital ellipse.

6.4.3.2.11 Polar Angle Scaled to Outer Extrema of Spherical Harmonics

As with the scaling method for the radial dimension in this system (and for linear displacement in systems treated earlier), we can also scale the polar angle in such a way that its nodes precisely align with those of the polar density distribution of the spherical harmonics $Y_l^m(\theta)$, which are, in effect, the minima of the Legendre polynomials in $\cos(\theta)$.

It is not clear why the minima of $P_m(\theta)$ do not naturally align with the minima of $Y_l^m(\theta)$, as there is no polar potential (i.e. no polar torque), and so we would expect the minima of $P_m(\theta)$ and $Y_l^m(\theta)$ to align, just as is the case with the minima of $P_m(\phi)$ and $Y_l^m(\phi)$, and the minima of the PIB system. It is noteworthy that the scaling factor for θ does align **all** extrema of $P_m(\phi)$ to $Y_l^m(\phi)$, and not just the outer maxima.

Additionally, we note that the gradient between the amplitude of $P_{mp}(\theta)$ at latitudes nearer the polar axis and latitudes nearer the equator is less than that exhibited by $Y_l^m(\theta)$. This smaller gradient may have to do with an exaggerated dwell time near the poles when τ_{ell} is smaller, perhaps?

The following plots show the same probability density distribution as plots (b) in section 6.4.3.2.10.1, but are scaled to the nodes of the Spherical Harmonics (showing only $m = 0, 1, 2, 3$ in this example because scaling has no effect for plots with one or fewer nodes, i.e., for $l - |m| \leq 1$):

For $n = 7, l = 5, m = 0$:

For $n = 7, l = 5, m = -1$:

For $n = 7, l = 5, m = -2$:

For $n = 7, l = 5, m = -3$:

6.4.3.2.11.1 Deviations of $P_{mp}(\theta)$ Amplitude From $Y_l^m(\theta)$ Amplitude

Inspection of graphical depictions

6.4.3.2.12 Form of $P_{mp}(\theta)$ and $P_{mp}(\phi)$

The expressions for $P_{mp}(\theta)$ and $P_{mp}(\phi)$ are the simple algebraic products:

$$P_{mp}(\theta_{eff}) = P_m(\theta_{eff}) \cdot P_p(\theta_{eff})$$

$$P_{mp}(\phi) = P_m(\phi) \cdot P_p(\phi)$$

In summary, recalling that:

$$\tau_{env} = \arcsin\left[\frac{l-l_\theta}{L}\right]$$

$$\theta_{eff}(\theta) = (\theta - \tau_{env}) \cdot \frac{\pi}{(\pi - 2\tau_{env})}$$

$$P_m(\theta_{eff}) = \cos^2\left[l_\theta \theta_{eff} + (1 - \delta_m) \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$$

$$P_m(\phi) = \cos^2\left[|m|\phi + (1 - \delta_{(|m|+m)}) \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$$

$$P_p'(\theta_{eff}) = \frac{l}{(1-\epsilon \cdot \cos[\theta_{eff}])} + \frac{l}{(1+\epsilon \cdot \cos[\theta_{eff}])}$$

$$P_p(\phi) = 1$$

We now have for the polar and azimuthal angular probabilities of measurable presence:

$$P_{mp}(\theta_{eff}) = \cos^2\left[l_\theta \theta_{eff} + (1 - \delta_m) \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}\right] \cdot \left[\frac{l}{(1-\epsilon \cdot \cos[\theta_{eff}])} + \frac{l}{(1+\epsilon \cdot \cos[\theta_{eff}])}\right]$$

$$P_{mp}(\phi) = \cos^2\left[|m|\phi + (1 - \delta_{(|m|+m)}) \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}\right] \cdot 1$$

6.4.3.2.13 Form of $P_{mp}(\theta, \phi)$

The expression for the probability density of measurable presence at any solid angular position is the simple algebraic product of $P_{mp}(\theta)$ and $P_{mp}(\phi)$:

$$P_{mp}(\theta, \phi) = P_{mp}(\theta) \cdot P_{mp}(\phi)$$

6.4.3.2.14 Graphical Depiction of $P_{mp}(\theta, \phi)$

Graphical depiction of $P_{mp}(\theta, \phi)$ in configuration space for a selected set of elliptical orbit declinations is illustrated in the following, with:

- No polar envelope, no polar probability of presence, no spherical harmonics outer extrema scaling.
Exhibits symmetric polar distribution of probability.
- Polar envelope, polar probability of presence, no outer extrema scaling
Exhibits compression within envelope toward equator (more evident for higher values of $|m|$), plus probability gradient from poles to equator (more evident for lower values of $|m|$). Differences between this gradient and that in (e) may be due to improper normalization of $P_{mp}(\theta, \phi)$.
- Canonical probability density distribution.

(a) (b) (c)
 $n = 7, l = 5, m = 0:$

$n = 7, l = 5, m = -1$:

$n = 7, l = 5, m = -2$:

$n = 7, l = 5, m = -3$:

$n = 7, l = 5, m = -4$:

$n = 7, l = 5, m = -5$:

6.4.3.2.15 Conclusions

In summary, it can be said that the effective polar angular domain and the probability of presence along the elliptical orbit trajectory (polar declined) combine to yield an effect on $P_m(\theta)$ that produces a 3-dimensional probability density distribution similar to that of the canonical model, accounting for the following significant characteristics:

1. Compression of the polar probability density distribution toward the equator for higher values of $|m|$ (or, equivalently, l_ϕ).
2. A gradient of probability of measurable presence – higher toward the poles and lower toward the equatorial region, with the gradient diminishing for higher values of m – that is consistent with the differences in orbital speed between periapsis and apoapsis, and the reduction of this effect for orbital planes of higher declination.

It is noteworthy that the combined effects of $P_m(\theta_{eff})$ and $P_p'(\theta_{eff})$ on the variation of probability density distribution with polar angular position match that of the (polar portion) of the spherical harmonics, $Y_l^m(\theta)$, with the former arising from the physics and geometry of the central-potential system and the latter apparently being a property of the spherical harmonics themselves.

6.4.4 Combined Radial and Angular Probability Density Distributions

When we combine the radial $P_{mp}(r)$ and solid angular $P_{mp}(\theta, \phi)$ measurable-presence probability density distributions, we obtain a 3-dimensional probability density distribution $P_{mp}(r, \theta, \phi)$, which depicts the probability of measuring a particle at any point in space around the central potential:

$$P_{mp}(r, \theta, \phi) = P_{mp}(r) \cdot P_{mp}(\theta, \phi)$$

We will examine how the probability density distributions of measurability and presence combine to yield $P_{mp}(r, \theta, \phi)$ by inspecting examples depicting the following compositions:

$$P_{m,m}(r, \theta, \phi) = P_m(r) \cdot P_m(\theta, \phi)$$

$$P_{mp,mp}(r, \theta, \phi) = P_{mp}(r) \cdot P_{mp}(\theta, \phi)$$

6.4.4.1 Graphical Depiction of $P_{mp}(\rho, \theta, \phi)$

The following plots depict representative examples of these variations of combined radial and angular 3D probability density distributions, along with corresponding plots of the canonical model. The spectral indices ($n = 6, l = 3, -l \leq m \leq 0$) were chosen to illustrate typical aspects of the model, which include the higher gradient of polar angular probability density between the poles and the equator for lower values of m and equatorial “compression” for higher values of m . A full catalog of 3D plots for spectral indices ($1 \leq n \leq 7$), ($0 \leq l \leq n - 1$), ($-l \leq m \leq +l$) can be found in appendix C.

For the following plots:

- Column (a) depicts $P_{m,m}(r, \theta, \phi)$
- Column (b) depicts $P_{mp,mp}(r, \theta, \phi)$
- Column (c) depicts the equivalent probability density distribution in the canonical model

The 3D plots are all from the viewpoint of the (+ X, - Y, + Z) corner of the bounding box.

(a)

(b)

(c)

$n = 7, l = 5, m = 0$:

$$\text{Re}[\Psi_{lm}(7,5,0)] = \text{Pmp}(7,5) + \text{PmpLu}(5,0), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$lu=5, \text{phu}=1, \text{lv}=0, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\Psi_{lm}(7,5,0)] = \text{PrepEnv}(7,5) + \text{PmpLuEnv}(5,0), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$lu=5, \text{phu}=1, \text{lv}=0, \text{phv}=0, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\Psi_{lm}(7,5,0)] = \text{PUH}(7,5) + \text{PYlm}(5,0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$n = 7, l = 5, m = -1$:

$$\text{Re}[\Psi_{lm}(7,5,-1)] = \text{Pmp}(7,5) + \text{PmpLu}(5,-1), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$lu=5, \text{phu}=0, \text{lv}=1, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\Psi_{lm}(7,5,-1)] = \text{PrepEnv}(7,5) + \text{PmpLuEnv}(5,-1), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$lu=5, \text{phu}=0, \text{lv}=1, \text{phv}=0, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\Psi_{lm}(7,5,-1)] = \text{PUH}(7,5) + \text{PYlm}(5,-1), \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$n = 7, l = 5, m = -2$:

$$\text{Re}[\Psi_{lm}(7,5,-2)] = \text{Pmp}(7,5) + \text{PmpLu}(5,-2), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$lu=4, \text{phu}=0, \text{lv}=2, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\Psi_{lm}(7,5,-2)] = \text{PrepEnv}(7,5) + \text{PmpLuEnv}(5,-2), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$lu=4, \text{phu}=0, \text{lv}=2, \text{phv}=0, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\Psi_{lm}(7,5,-2)] = \text{PUH}(7,5) + \text{PYlm}(5,-2), \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$n = 7, l = 5, m = -3$:

$n = 7, l = 5, m = -4:$

$n = 7, l = 5, m = -5:$

As can be seen, merely the combined probability densities of radial and angular measurability yield the rough geometry of probability density distribution that is characteristic of the atomic orbitals. Layering on the effect of the polar angular envelope (θ_{eff}) and the probability densities of radial and angular presence further refines these density distributions to reflect the same shifts in shading and shape of orbitals that are characteristic of the canonical model. For example:

1. A higher gradient occurs between polar and equatorial regions, with reduced density around the equatorial belt for lower values of $|m|$

2. A “compressing” of the lobes toward the equator within an equatorial belt delimited by the declined elliptical orbit plane occurs, having greater effect for higher values of $|m|$

6.5 Non-Radiation of Charged Particle in Accelerated Motion

In the case that a material body is a charged particle (e.g. electron), it would be expected that this accelerating particle would radiate energy. But work by H. Puthoff (<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1204.1952>, and <https://journals.aps.org/prd/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevD.35.3266>) suggests otherwise for such systems in a ground state.

Appendices

A - Relationship of $Y_l^m(\theta)$ to $P_m(\theta)$ As the following table illustrates, the structure of the trigonometric polynomials in θ resulting from the expansion of $P_{l,m}(\theta)$ exhibit a degree of similarity to the structure of the trigonometric polynomials that make up the spherical harmonics $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$ in θ (i.e., they are of the same degree and have the same number of terms, with the same exponents, and with corresponding terms having similarly proportioned coefficients). The spherical harmonics include an additional factor $\sin^q[\theta]$, where $q = |m| - 1$, the effect of which on the polar angular distribution of probability density is achieved by a different mathematical construct for $P_{mp}(\theta)$.

A.1 Tabulation of $Y_l^m(\theta)$ vs. $\sqrt{P_m(\theta)}$

l	$ m $	$Y_l^m(\theta)$	$\sqrt{P_m(\theta)}$
1	0	$\sqrt{\frac{3}{4\pi}} \cos[\theta]$	$\cos[1\theta] = \cos[\theta]$

1	1	$\sqrt{\frac{3}{8\pi}} \sin[\theta]$	$\sin[1\theta] = \sin[\theta]$
2	0	$\sqrt{\frac{5}{16\pi}} (3\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$	$\cos[2\theta] = (2\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$
2	1	$\sqrt{\frac{15}{8\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta]$	$\sin[2\theta] = 2 \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta]$
2	2	$\sqrt{\frac{15}{32\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cdot \sin[\theta]$	$\sin[1\theta] = \sin[\theta]$
3	0	$\sqrt{\frac{7}{16\pi}} \cos[\theta] (5\cos^2[\theta] - 3)$	$\cos[3\theta] = \cos[\theta] (4\cos^2[\theta] - 3)$
3	1	$\sqrt{\frac{21}{64\pi}} \sin[\theta] (5\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$	$\sin[3\theta] = \sin[\theta] (4\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$
3	2	$\sqrt{\frac{105}{32\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] \cdot \sin[\theta]$	$\sin[2\theta] = 2 \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta]$
3	3	$\sqrt{\frac{35}{64\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cdot \sin^2[\theta]$	$\sin[1\theta] = \sin[\theta]$
4	0	$\sqrt{\frac{9}{256\pi}} (35\cos^4[\theta] - 30\cos^2[\theta] + 3)$	$\cos[4\theta] = (8\cos^4[\theta] - 8\cos^2[\theta] + 1)$
4	1	$\sqrt{\frac{45}{64\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] \cdot (7\cos^2[\theta] - 3)$	$\sin[4\theta] = 4 \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (2\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$
4	2	$\sqrt{\frac{45}{128\pi}} \sin[\theta] (7\cos^2[\theta] - 1) \cdot \sin[\theta]$	$\sin[3\theta] = \sin[\theta] (4\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$
4	3	$\sqrt{\frac{315}{64\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] \cdot \sin^2[\theta]$	$\sin[2\theta] = 2 \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta]$
4	4	$\sqrt{\frac{315}{512\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cdot \sin^3[\theta]$	$\sin[1\theta] = \sin[\theta]$
5	0	$\sqrt{\frac{11}{256\pi}} \cos[\theta] (63\cos^4[\theta] - 70\cos^2[\theta] + 15)$	$\cos[5\theta] = \cos[\theta] (16\cos^4[\theta] - 20\cos^2[\theta] + 5)$
5	1	$\sqrt{\frac{165}{512\pi}} \sin[\theta] (21\cos^4[\theta] - 14\cos^2[\theta] + 1)$	$\sin[5\theta] = \sin[\theta] (16\cos^4[\theta] - 12\cos^2[\theta] + 1)$
5	2	$\sqrt{\frac{1155}{128\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (3\cos^2[\theta] - 1) \cdot \sin[\theta]$	$\sin[4\theta] = 4 \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (2\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$
5	3	$\sqrt{\frac{385}{1024\pi}} \sin[\theta] (9\cos^2[\theta] - 1) \cdot \sin^2[\theta]$	$\sin[3\theta] = \sin[\theta] (4\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$

5	4	$\sqrt{\frac{3465}{512\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] \cdot \sin^3[\theta]$	$\sin[2\theta] = 2 \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta]$
5	5	$\sqrt{\frac{693}{1024\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cdot \sin^4[\theta]$	$\sin[1\theta] = \sin[\theta]$
6	0	$\sqrt{\frac{13}{1024\pi}} (231\cos^6[\theta] - 315\cos^4[\theta] + 105\cos^2[\theta] - 5)$	$\cos[6\theta] = (32\cos^6[\theta] - 48\cos^4[\theta] + 18\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$
6	1	$\sqrt{\frac{273}{512\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (33\cos^4[\theta] - 30\cos^2[\theta] + 5)$	$\sin[6\theta] = \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (32\cos^4[\theta] - 32\cos^2[\theta] + 6)$
6	2	$\sqrt{\frac{1365}{4096\pi}} \sin[\theta] (33\cos^4[\theta] - 18\cos^2[\theta] + 1) \cdot \sin[\theta]$	$\sin[5\theta] = \sin[\theta] (16\cos^4[\theta] - 12\cos^2[\theta] + 1)$
6	3	$\sqrt{\frac{1365}{1024\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (11\cos^2[\theta] - 3) \cdot \sin^2[\theta]$	$\sin[4\theta] = 4\sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (2\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$
6	4	$\sqrt{\frac{819}{2048\pi}} \sin[\theta] (11\cos^2[\theta] - 1) \cdot \sin^3[\theta]$	$\sin[3\theta] = \sin[\theta] (4\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$
6	5	$\sqrt{\frac{9009}{1024\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] \cdot \sin^4[\theta]$	$\sin[2\theta] = 2 \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta]$
6	6	$\sqrt{\frac{3003}{4096\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cdot \sin^5[\theta]$	$\sin[1\theta] = \sin[\theta]$
7	0	$\sqrt{\frac{15}{1024\pi}} \cos[\theta] (429\cos^6[\theta] - 693\cos^4[\theta] + 315\cos^2[\theta] - 35)$	$\cos[7\theta] = \cos[\theta] (64\cos^6[\theta] - 112\cos^4[\theta] + 56\cos^2[\theta] - 7)$
7	1	$\sqrt{\frac{105}{256\pi}} \sin[\theta] (429\cos^6[\theta] - 495\cos^4[\theta] + 135\cos^2[\theta] - 5)$	$\sin[7\theta] = \sin[\theta] (64\cos^6[\theta] - 80\cos^4[\theta] + 24\cos^2[\theta] - 7)$
7	2	$\sqrt{\frac{315}{4096\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (143\cos^4[\theta] - 110\cos^2[\theta] + 15) \cdot \sin[\theta]$	$\sin[6\theta] = \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (32\cos^4[\theta] - 32\cos^2[\theta] + 6)$
7	3	$\sqrt{\frac{315}{8192\pi}} \sin[\theta] (143\cos^4[\theta] - 66\cos^2[\theta] + 3) \cdot \sin^2[\theta]$	$\sin[5\theta] = \sin[\theta] (16\cos^4[\theta] - 12\cos^2[\theta] + 1)$
7	4	$\sqrt{\frac{3465}{2048\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (13\cos^2[\theta] - 3) \cdot \sin^3[\theta]$	$\sin[4\theta] = 4\sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] (2\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$
7	5	$\sqrt{\frac{3465}{8192\pi}} \sin[\theta] (13\cos^2[\theta] - 1) \cdot \sin^4[\theta]$	$\sin[3\theta] = \sin[\theta] (4\cos^2[\theta] - 1)$
7	6	$\sqrt{\frac{45045}{4096\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta] \cdot \sin^5[\theta]$	$\sin[2\theta] = 2 \sin[\theta] \cos[\theta]$
7	7	$\sqrt{\frac{6435}{8192\pi}} \sin[\theta] \cdot \sin^6[\theta]$	$\sin[1\theta] = \sin[\theta]$

A.2 Tabulation of $Y_l^m(\theta) / \sqrt{P_m(\theta)}$

The following table documents the algebraic quotient (for the selected range $1 \leq l \leq 7$ and $0 \leq |m| \leq l$) for the θ -dependent factors of $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$ in the quotient $\frac{Y_l^m(\theta)}{\sqrt{P_m(\theta)}}$. For use in this table, we define the expression $T_{l,m}(\theta)$, which has the effect of biasing the probability density toward the equatorial plane (i.e., near the “tropics,” hence “T”):

$$T_{l,m}(\theta) \equiv \frac{\sin[\theta]^{(|m|-1+\delta_m)}}{2^{(l-|m|-\delta_m)}}$$

We also define the expression $\Pi_{l,m}(\theta)$, which has the effect of biasing the probability density toward the poles (hence “Π”):

$$\Pi_{l,m}(\theta) \equiv \frac{\sum_{q=0}^{\text{Floor}[\frac{l-|m|}{2}]} CN_{l,m,q} \cos[2q\theta]}{\sum_{q=0}^{\text{Floor}[\frac{l-|m|}{2}]} CD_{l,m,q} \cos[2q\theta]}$$

For the coefficients of the **numerator** polynomial:

$$CN_{l,m,q} = \delta_{q,0} \cdot (\delta_{m,l} + \delta_{m,l-1}) + ()$$

$CN_{l,m,q=0}$ seems to be related to prime numbers, and the $(2l - 3)$ pattern for case $\text{Floor}[\frac{(l-|m|)}{2}] = 1$ is likely not relevant (i.e., primes seem to be a more likely pattern).

$CN_{l,m,q=\text{Floor}[\frac{l-|m|}{2}]}$ clearly always involves a factor of $(2l - 1)$

For the coefficients of the **denominator** polynomial:

$$CD_{l,m,q} = \delta_{q,0} \cdot (\delta_{m,l} + \delta_{m,l-1}) + ()$$

l	$ m $	Quotient $\frac{Y_l^m(\theta)}{\sqrt{P_m(\theta)}}$	Quotient Generator
1	0	$\sqrt{\frac{3}{4\pi}} \cdot 1$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)}{4\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
1	1	$\sqrt{\frac{3}{8\pi}} \cdot 1$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)}{8\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
2	0	$\sqrt{\frac{5}{16\pi}} \cdot \frac{(3\cos[2\theta]+1)}{2\cos[2\theta]}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)}{16\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{((2l-1)\cdot\cos[2\theta]+1)}{(\cos[2\theta]+(0))}$
2	1	$\sqrt{\frac{15}{8\pi}} \cdot \frac{1}{2}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(l+1)\cdot(2l+1)}{8\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$

2	2	$\sqrt{\frac{15}{32\pi}} \cdot \sin[\theta]$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{32\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
3	0	$\sqrt{\frac{7}{16\pi}} \cdot \frac{(5\cos[2\theta]-1)}{2(2\cos[2\theta]-1)}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)}{16\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{((2l-1) \cdot \cos[2\theta]-1)}{(\cos[2\theta]-\frac{1}{2})}$
3	1	$\sqrt{\frac{21}{64\pi}} \cdot \frac{(5\cos[2\theta]+3)}{4(\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{l \cdot (2l+1)}{64\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{((2l-1) \cdot \cos[2\theta]+3)}{(\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$
3	2	$\sqrt{\frac{105}{32\pi}} \cdot \sin[\theta] \cdot \frac{1}{2}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{5 \cdot l \cdot (2l+1)}{32\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
3	3	$\sqrt{\frac{35}{64\pi}} \cdot \sin^2[\theta]$	$= \sqrt{\frac{5 \cdot (2l+1)}{64\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
4	0	$\sqrt{\frac{9}{256\pi}} \cdot \frac{(35\cos[4\theta]+20\cos[2\theta]+9)}{8(\cos[4\theta]+0)}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)}{256\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(5 \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[4\theta]+2 \cdot 2 \cdot 5 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+3 \cdot 3)}{(\cos[4\theta]+(0 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+0))}$
4	1	$\sqrt{\frac{45}{64\pi}} \cdot \frac{(7\cos[2\theta]+1)}{8\cos[2\theta]}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{64\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{((2l-1) \cdot \cos[2\theta]+1)}{(\cos[2\theta]+(0))}$
4	2	$\sqrt{\frac{45}{128\pi}} \cdot \sin[\theta] \cdot \frac{(7\cos[2\theta]+5)}{4(\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{128\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{((2l-1) \cdot \cos[2\theta]+(2l-3))}{(\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$
4	3	$\sqrt{\frac{315}{64\pi}} \cdot \sin^2[\theta] \cdot \frac{1}{2}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{7 \cdot (l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{64\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
4	4	$\sqrt{\frac{315}{512\pi}} \cdot \sin^3[\theta]$	$= \sqrt{\frac{7 \cdot (l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{512\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
5	0	$\sqrt{\frac{11}{256\pi}} \cdot \frac{(63\cos[4\theta]-28\cos[2\theta]+29)}{8(2\cos[4\theta]-2\cos[2\theta]+1)}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)}{256\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(7 \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[4\theta]-2 \cdot 2 \cdot 7 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+29)}{(\cos[4\theta]-\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$
5	1	$\sqrt{\frac{165}{512\pi}} \cdot \frac{(21\cos[4\theta]+28\cos[2\theta]+15)}{16(\cos[4\theta]+\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot l \cdot (2l+1)}{8^3 \pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(7 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[4\theta]+2 \cdot 2 \cdot 7 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+3 \cdot 5)}{(\cos[4\theta]+\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$
5	2	$\sqrt{\frac{1155}{128\pi}} \cdot \sin[\theta] \cdot \frac{(3\cos[2\theta]+1)}{8 \cdot \cos[2\theta]}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 7 \cdot l \cdot (2l+1)}{128\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(\frac{1}{3} \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[2\theta]+1)}{(\cos[2\theta]+(0))}$
5	3	$\sqrt{\frac{385}{1024\pi}} \cdot \sin^2[\theta] \cdot \frac{(9\cos[2\theta]+7)}{4(\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{7 \cdot l \cdot (2l+1)}{1024\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{((2l-1) \cdot \cos[2\theta]+(2l-3))}{(\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$
5	4	$\sqrt{\frac{3465}{512\pi}} \cdot \sin^3[\theta] \cdot \frac{1}{2}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 3 \cdot 7 \cdot l \cdot (2l+1)}{512\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
5	5	$\sqrt{\frac{693}{1024\pi}} \cdot \sin^4[\theta]$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 3 \cdot 7 \cdot (2l+1)}{1024\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
6	0	$\sqrt{\frac{13}{1024\pi}} \cdot \frac{(231\cos[6\theta]+126\cos[4\theta]+105\cos[2\theta]+50)}{32(\cos[6\theta]+0)}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)}{1024\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(3 \cdot 7 \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[6\theta]+2 \cdot 3 \cdot 3 \cdot 7 \cdot \cos[4\theta]+3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+2 \cdot 5 \cdot 5)}{(\cos[6\theta]+(0 \cdot \cos[4\theta]+0 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+0))}$

6	1	$\sqrt{\frac{273}{512\pi}} \cdot \frac{(33\cos[4\theta]+12\cos[2\theta]+19)}{32(\cos[4\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot (l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{8^3 \pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(3 \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[4\theta]+2 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+19)}{(\cos[4\theta]+(0 \cdot \cos[2\theta])+\frac{1}{2})}$
6	2	$\sqrt{\frac{1365}{4096\pi}} \cdot \sin[\theta] \cdot \frac{(33\cos[4\theta]+60\cos[2\theta]+35)}{16(\cos[4\theta]+\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 5 \cdot (l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{4096\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(3 \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[4\theta]+3 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 5 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+5 \cdot 7)}{(\cos[4\theta]+\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$
6	3	$\sqrt{\frac{1365}{1024\pi}} \cdot \sin^2[\theta] \cdot \frac{(11\cos[2\theta]+5)}{8\cos[2\theta]}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 5 \cdot (l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{1024\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{((2l-1) \cdot \cos[2\theta]+5)}{(\cos[2\theta]+(0))}$
6	4	$\sqrt{\frac{819}{2048\pi}} \cdot \sin^3[\theta] \cdot \frac{(11\cos[2\theta]+9)}{4(\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 3 \cdot (l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{2048\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{((2l-1) \cdot \cos[2\theta]+(2l-3))}{(\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$
6	5	$\sqrt{\frac{9009}{1024\pi}} \cdot \sin^4[\theta] \cdot \frac{1}{2}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 3 \cdot 11 \cdot (l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{1024\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
6	6	$\sqrt{\frac{3003}{4096\pi}} \cdot \sin^5[\theta]$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 11 \cdot (l+1) \cdot (2l+1)}{4096\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
7	0	$\sqrt{\frac{15}{1024\pi}} \cdot \frac{(429\cos[6\theta]-198\cos[4\theta]+387\cos[2\theta]-106)}{32(2\cos[6\theta]-2\cos[4\theta]+2\cos[2\theta]-1)}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{(2l+1)}{1024\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(11 \cdot 3 \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[6\theta]-2 \cdot 3 \cdot 3 \cdot 11 \cdot \cos[4\theta]+3 \cdot 3 \cdot 43 \cos[2\theta]-2 \cdot 53)}{(\cos[6\theta]-\cos[4\theta]+\cos[2\theta]-\frac{1}{2})}$
7	1	$\sqrt{\frac{105}{8192\pi}} \cdot \frac{(429\cos[6\theta]+594\cos[4\theta]+675\cos[2\theta]+350)}{64(\cos[6\theta]+\cos[4\theta]+\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{l \cdot (2l+1)}{8192\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(11 \cdot 3 \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[6\theta]+2 \cdot 3 \cdot 3 \cdot 11 \cdot \cos[4\theta]+3 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 5 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+2 \cdot 5 \cdot 5 \cdot 7)}{(\cos[6\theta]+\cos[4\theta]+\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$
7	2	$\sqrt{\frac{315}{4096\pi}} \cdot \sin[\theta] \cdot \frac{(143\cos[4\theta]+132\cos[2\theta]+109)}{32(\cos[4\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot l \cdot (2l+1)}{4096\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(11 \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[4\theta]+2 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 11 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+109)}{(\cos[4\theta]+(0 \cdot \cos[2\theta])+\frac{1}{2})}$
7	3	$\sqrt{\frac{315}{8192\pi}} \cdot \sin^2[\theta] \cdot \frac{(143\cos[4\theta]+308\cos[2\theta]+189)}{16(\cos[4\theta]+\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot l \cdot (2l+1)}{8192\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{(11 \cdot (2l-1) \cdot \cos[4\theta]+2 \cdot 2 \cdot 7 \cdot 11 \cdot \cos[2\theta]+3 \cdot 3 \cdot 3 \cdot 7)}{(\cos[4\theta]+\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$
7	4	$\sqrt{\frac{3465}{2048\pi}} \cdot \sin^3[\theta] \cdot \frac{(13\cos[2\theta]+7)}{8\cos[2\theta]}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 11 \cdot l \cdot (2l+1)}{2048\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{((2l-1) \cdot \cos[2\theta]+7)}{(\cos[2\theta]+(0))}$
7	5	$\sqrt{\frac{3465}{8192\pi}} \cdot \sin^4[\theta] \cdot \frac{(13\cos[2\theta]+11)}{4(\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 11 \cdot l \cdot (2l+1)}{8192\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta) \cdot \frac{((2l-1) \cdot \cos[2\theta]+(2l-3))}{(\cos[2\theta]+\frac{1}{2})}$
7	6	$\sqrt{\frac{45045}{4096\pi}} \cdot \sin^5[\theta] \cdot \frac{1}{2}$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 11 \cdot 13 \cdot l \cdot (2l+1)}{4096\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$
7	7	$\sqrt{\frac{6435}{8192\pi}} \cdot \sin^6[\theta]$	$= \sqrt{\frac{3 \cdot 11 \cdot 13 \cdot (2l+1)}{8192\pi}} \cdot T_{l,m}(\theta)$

B - Tabulation of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$

The following table illustrates the graphical results of the composition of $\sqrt{P_m(\theta, \phi)}$ from $\sqrt{P_m(\theta)}$ and $\sqrt{P_m(\phi)}$ (for $0 \leq l_\theta \leq 6$, $-l_\theta \leq l_\phi \leq l_\theta$):

l	l_θ	m	l_ϕ	3D Density Plot of $\left(\sqrt{P_m(\theta, \phi)}\right)^2$
0	0	0	0	
1	1	0	0	
1	1	- 1	1	
		+ 1	1	
2	2	0	0	
2	2	- 1	1	
		+ 1	1	
2	1	- 2	2	
		+ 2	2	
3	3	0	0	
3	3	- 1	1	
		+ 1	1	

3	2	- 2	2	
3	1	- 3	3	
4	4	0	0	
4	4	- 1	1	
4	3	- 2	2	
4	2	- 3	3	
4	1	- 4	4	

5	5	0	0	
5	5	- 1	1	
5	4	- 2	2	
5	3	- 3	3	
5	2	- 4	4	
5	1	- 5	5	
6	6	0	0	
6	6	- 1	1	

6	5	- 2	2	
		+ 2	2	
6	4	- 3	3	
		+ 3	3	
6	3	- 4	4	
		+ 4	4	
6	2	- 5	5	
		+ 5	5	
6	1	- 6	6	
		+ 6	6	

C - Tabulation of $P_{mp}(r, \theta, \phi)$ for the Central Potential

The following are plots of the combined radial and angular probability density distributions of measurable presence $P_{mp}(r, \theta, \phi)$.

In the following plots:

- Column (a) depicts $P_{mp}(r, \theta, \phi)$ with no “outer extrema scaling” to the canonical model (i.e., scaling to outer radial or polar angular nodes of the canonical model).
- Column (b) depicts the canonical model: $\left[R_{nl}(r) \cdot Y_l^m(\theta, \phi) \right]^2$
- Column (c) depicts $P_{mp}(r, \theta, \phi)$ **with** “outer extrema scaling” to the canonical model

(a) $n=1, l=0, m=0$:

(b)

(c)

$n=2, l=0, m=0$:

Re[Ylm[2,0,0]] = PUn[2,0] + PYln[0,0], Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

Re[Ylm[2,0,0]] = PmpEnv[2,0] + PmpluvEnv[0,0], Xi=1
lu=0, phi=1, lv=0, phv=1, RadFract=10.0(14.6282), Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

$n=2, l=1, m=0$:

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(2,1,0) = P_{\text{pr}}E_{\text{m}}(2,1) + P_{\text{m}}U_{\text{m}}E_{\text{m}}(1,0), X_{l=1}$
 $l=1, \text{pha}=1, \text{lv}=0, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=(12.14398.0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2.4,2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(2,1,0) = P_{U}(2,1) + P_{Y}(1,0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2.4,2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(2,1,0) = P_{\text{pr}}E_{\text{m}}(2,1) + P_{\text{m}}U_{\text{m}}E_{\text{m}}(1,0), X_{l=1}$
 $l=1, \text{pha}=1, \text{lv}=0, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=1, \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2.4,2)$

n=2, l=1, m=1

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(2,1,1) = P_{\text{pr}}E_{\text{m}}(2,1) + P_{\text{m}}U_{\text{m}}E_{\text{m}}(1,1), X_{l=1}$
 $l=1, \text{pha}=0, \text{lv}=1, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=(12.14398.0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2.4,2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(2,1,1) = P_{U}(2,1) + P_{Y}(1,1), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2.4,2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(2,1,1) = P_{\text{pr}}E_{\text{m}}(2,1) + P_{\text{m}}U_{\text{m}}E_{\text{m}}(1,1), X_{l=1}$
 $l=1, \text{pha}=0, \text{lv}=1, \text{phv}=0, \text{RadFract}=1, \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2.4,2)$

n=2, l=1, m=-1

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(2,1,-1) = P_{\text{pr}}E_{\text{m}}(2,1) + P_{\text{m}}U_{\text{m}}E_{\text{m}}(1,-1), X_{l=1}$
 $l=1, \text{pha}=0, \text{lv}=1, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=(12.14398.0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2.4,2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(2,1,-1) = P_{U}(2,1) + P_{Y}(1,-1), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2.4,2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(2,1,-1) = P_{\text{pr}}E_{\text{m}}(2,1) + P_{\text{m}}U_{\text{m}}E_{\text{m}}(1,-1), X_{l=1}$
 $l=1, \text{pha}=0, \text{lv}=1, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=1, \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2.4,2)$

n=3, l=0, m=0:

n=3, l=1, m=0:

n=3, l=1, m=1:

n=3, l=1, m=-1:

n=3, l=2, m=2:

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(3,2,2) = \text{PprpEn}(3,2) + \text{PmPluEn}(2,2), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l_u=1, \text{pha}=0, l_v=2, \text{phv}=0, \text{RadFract}=(23.6253/18.0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(3,2,2) = \text{PUH}(3,2) + \text{PYIn}(2,2), \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(3,2,2) = \text{PprpEn}(3,2) + \text{PmPluEn}(2,2), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l_u=1, \text{pha}=0, l_v=2, \text{phv}=0, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

n=3, l=2, m=-2:

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(3,2,-2) = \text{PprpEn}(3,2) + \text{PmPluEn}(2,-2), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l_u=1, \text{pha}=0, l_v=2, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=(23.6253/18.0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(3,2,-2) = \text{PUH}(3,2) + \text{PYIn}(2,-2), \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(3,2,-2) = \text{PprpEn}(3,2) + \text{PmPluEn}(2,-2), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l_u=1, \text{pha}=0, l_v=2, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

n=4, l=0, m=0:

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,0,0) = \text{PprpEn}(4,0) + \text{PmPluEn}(0,0), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l_u=0, \text{pha}=1, l_v=0, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=(45.8337/32.0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,0,0) = \text{PUH}(4,0) + \text{PYIn}(0,0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,0,0) = \text{PprpEn}(4,0) + \text{PmPluEn}(0,0), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l_u=0, \text{pha}=1, l_v=0, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$$

n=4, l=1, m=0:

Re[Ylm(4,1,0)] = PmprEnv(4,1) + PmpluvEnv(1,0), Xi=1
 lu=1, phz=1, lv=0, phv=1, RadFract=(44.5768/32.0), Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

Re[Ylm(4,1,0)] = PUh(4,1) + PYln(1,0), Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

Re[Ylm(4,1,0)] = PmprEnv(4,1) + PmpluvEnv(1,0), Xi=1
 lu=1, phz=1, lv=0, phv=1, RadFract=1.0, Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

n=4, l=1, m=1:

Re[Ylm(4,1,1)] = PmprEnv(4,1) + PmpluvEnv(1,1), Xi=1
 lu=1, phz=0, lv=1, phv=0, RadFract=(44.5768/32.0), Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

Re[Ylm(4,1,1)] = PUh(4,1) + PYln(1,1), Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

Re[Ylm(4,1,1)] = PmprEnv(4,1) + PmpluvEnv(1,1), Xi=1
 lu=1, phz=0, lv=1, phv=0, RadFract=1.0, Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

n=4, l=1, m=-1:

Re[Ylm(4,1,-1)] = PmprEnv(4,1) + PmpluvEnv(1,-1), Xi=1
 lu=1, phz=0, lv=1, phv=1, RadFract=(44.5768/32.0), Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

Re[Ylm(4,1,-1)] = PUh(4,1) + PYln(1,-1), Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

Re[Ylm(4,1,-1)] = PmprEnv(4,1) + PmpluvEnv(1,-1), Xi=1
 lu=1, phz=0, lv=1, phv=1, RadFract=1.0, Vpt=(1.3,-2.4,2)

n=4, l=2, m=0:

n=4, l=2, m=1:

n=4, l=2, m=-1:

n=4, l=2, m=2:

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,2,2)] = \text{PmpPrEnV}(4,2) + \text{PmPluVEn}(2,2), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l=1, \text{pha}=0, l=2, \text{phv}=0, \text{RadFract}=(43.886132,0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2,4,2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,2,2)] = \text{PUH}(4,2) + \text{PYlm}(2,2), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2,4,2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,2,2)] = \text{PmpPrEnV}(4,2) + \text{PmPluVEn}(2,2), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l=1, \text{pha}=0, l=2, \text{phv}=0, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2,4,2)$$

n=4, l=2, m=-2:

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,2,-2)] = \text{PmpPrEnV}(4,2) + \text{PmPluVEn}(2,-2), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l=1, \text{pha}=0, l=2, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=(43.886132,0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2,4,2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,2,-2)] = \text{PUH}(4,2) + \text{PYlm}(2,-2), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2,4,2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,2,-2)] = \text{PmpPrEnV}(4,2) + \text{PmPluVEn}(2,-2), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l=1, \text{pha}=0, l=2, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2,4,2)$$

n=4, l=3, m=0:

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,3,0)] = \text{PmpPrEnV}(4,3) + \text{PmPluVEn}(3,0), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l=3, \text{pha}=1, l=0, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=(38.50732,0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2,4,2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,3,0)] = \text{PUH}(4,3) + \text{PYlm}(3,0), \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2,4,2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,3,0)] = \text{PmpPrEnV}(4,3) + \text{PmPluVEn}(3,0), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l=3, \text{pha}=1, l=0, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt}=(1.3,-2,4,2)$$

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,3,0)] = \text{PmpPrEnV}(4,3) + \text{PmPluVEn}(3,0), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l=3, \text{pha}=1, l=0, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=(38.50732,0), \text{Vpt=Front}$$

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,3,0)] = \text{PUH}(4,3) + \text{PYlm}(3,0), \text{Vpt=Front}$$

$$\text{Re}[\text{Ylm}(4,3,0)] = \text{PmpPrEnV}(4,3) + \text{PmPluVEn}(3,0), \text{Xi}=1$$

$$l=3, \text{pha}=1, l=0, \text{phv}=1, \text{RadFract}=1.0, \text{Vpt=Front}$$

n=4, l=3, m=1:

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,1) = P_{mp}E_{lm}(4,3) + P_{m}Y_{lm}(3,1)$, $X_l=1$
 $l=3, \text{phv}=0, l_v=1, \text{phv}_v=0, \text{RadFract}=(38.507/32.0)$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,1) = P_{Um}(4,3) + P_{Ylm}(3,1)$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,1) = P_{mp}E_{lm}(4,3) + P_{m}Y_{lm}(3,1)$, $X_l=1$
 $l=3, \text{phv}=0, l_v=1, \text{phv}_v=0, \text{RadFract}=1.0$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

n=4, l=3, m=-1

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,-1) = P_{mp}E_{lm}(4,3) + P_{m}Y_{lm}(3,-1)$, $X_l=1$
 $l=3, \text{phv}=0, l_v=1, \text{phv}_v=0, \text{RadFract}=(38.507/32.0)$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,-1) = P_{Um}(4,3) + P_{Ylm}(3,-1)$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,-1) = P_{mp}E_{lm}(4,3) + P_{m}Y_{lm}(3,-1)$, $X_l=1$
 $l=3, \text{phv}=0, l_v=1, \text{phv}_v=0, \text{RadFract}=1.0$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

n=4, l=3, m=2:

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,2) = P_{mp}E_{lm}(4,3) + P_{m}Y_{lm}(3,2)$, $X_l=1$
 $l=2, \text{phv}=0, l_v=2, \text{phv}_v=0, \text{RadFract}=(38.507/32.0)$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,2) = P_{Um}(4,3) + P_{Ylm}(3,2)$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,2) = P_{mp}E_{lm}(4,3) + P_{m}Y_{lm}(3,2)$, $X_l=1$
 $l=2, \text{phv}=0, l_v=2, \text{phv}_v=0, \text{RadFract}=1.0$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

n=4, l=3, m=-2:

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,-2) = P_{mp}E_{lm}(4,3) + P_{m}Y_{lm}(3,-2)$, $X_l=1$
 $l=2, \text{phv}=0, l_v=2, \text{phv}_v=0, \text{RadFract}=(38.507/32.0)$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,-2) = P_{Um}(4,3) + P_{Ylm}(3,-2)$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,-2) = P_{mp}E_{lm}(4,3) + P_{m}Y_{lm}(3,-2)$, $X_l=1$
 $l=2, \text{phv}=0, l_v=2, \text{phv}_v=0, \text{RadFract}=1.0$, $V_{pt}=(1.3, -2.4, 2)$

n=4, l=3, m=3:

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,3) = P_{33}E_{4,3} + P_{31}E_{4,3} + P_{30}E_{4,3}, X_{l=1}$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,3) = P_{33}E_{4,3} + P_{31}E_{4,3} + P_{30}E_{4,3}, Y_{l=1}$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,3) = P_{33}E_{4,3} + P_{31}E_{4,3} + P_{30}E_{4,3}, X_{l=1}$$

n=4, l=3, m=3:

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,-3) = P_{33}E_{4,3} + P_{31}E_{4,3} + P_{30}E_{4,3}, X_{l=1}$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,-3) = P_{33}E_{4,3} + P_{31}E_{4,3} + P_{30}E_{4,3}, Y_{l=1}$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(4,3,-3) = P_{33}E_{4,3} + P_{31}E_{4,3} + P_{30}E_{4,3}, X_{l=1}$$

n=6, l=4, m=2:

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(6,4,-2) = P_{42}E_{6,4} + P_{40}E_{6,4} + P_{4-2}E_{6,4}, X_{l=1}$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(6,4,-2) = P_{42}E_{6,4} + P_{40}E_{6,4} + P_{4-2}E_{6,4}, Y_{l=1}$$

$$\text{Re}Y_{lm}(6,4,-2) = P_{42}E_{6,4} + P_{40}E_{6,4} + P_{4-2}E_{6,4}, X_{l=1}$$

n=6, l=4, m=3:

n=7, l=4, m=-1:

n=7, l=6, m=-3:

n=7, l=6, m=-1:

D - Illustration of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ vs. $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$

The following plots illustrate variations for certain aspects of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ and $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$, as described in section 6.4.3.2.4.2. In addition, we include plots of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ using values of $l_\theta, \Phi_\theta, l_\phi, \Phi_\phi$ that make corresponding aspects of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ exhibit characteristics similar to those of $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$. For now, these values of $l_\theta, \Phi_\theta, l_\phi, \Phi_\phi$ appear to be arbitrary. However, we will later see that physical aspects of the central-potential system will impose constraints on the values of $l_\theta, \Phi_\theta, l_\phi, \Phi_\phi$ that yield a close correspondence between the spatial structure of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ and $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$.

In these images, the values of $l_\theta, \Phi_\theta, l_\phi, \Phi_\phi$ vary across columns ($0 \leq l_\phi \leq 5$) along with the values of l, m for $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$. The rows depict various aspects of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ and $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$ for each of the columns. Plots of $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$ are shown in **green**, while plots of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ are shown in **blue**.

$l_\theta = 5$	$l_\theta = 5$	$l_\theta = 4$	$l_\theta = 3$	$l_\theta = 2$	$l_\theta = 1$
$\Phi_\theta = 1$	$\Phi_\theta = 0$				
$l_\phi = 0$	$l_\phi = 1$	$l_\phi = 2$	$l_\phi = 3$	$l_\phi = 4$	$l_\phi = 5$
$\Phi_\phi = 0$	$\Phi_\phi = 1$				
$l = 5$					
$ m = 0$	$ m = 1$	$ m = 2$	$ m = 3$	$ m = 4$	$ m = 5$

Variation with polar angle ($0 \leq \theta \leq \pi$) of $P_m(\theta)$ in blue and $Y_l^m(\theta)$ in green:

Cross section in the plane $y = 0$ of density plot of $P_m(\theta)$:

Cross section in the plane $y = 0$ of density plot of $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$:

Density plot of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ viewed obliquely:

Density plot of $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$ viewed obliquely:

Density plot of $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ viewed from the front:

Density plot of $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$ viewed from the front:

The structural differences between $P_m(\theta, \phi)$ and $Y_l^m(\theta, \phi)$ will be eliminated by imposing constraints on $l_\theta, \Phi_\theta, l_\phi, \Phi_\phi$ and θ that arise from physical aspects of the central-potential system.

References

[1] - Boll, D. - Special Relativity's Light-Signal Mediated Definition of Synchronism is Without Contradictions Only in Phase Space When Considering the Quantum Behavior of Light - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15562198>

Although the premise of that paper has turned out to likely be false, that does not preclude some other physical justification (other than that asserted in the premise) for the scalar field of measurability, which is the basis for most of that paper, and for all of this paper.